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NAUTILOS will fill-in marine observation and modelling gaps for chemical, biological and deep ocean physics variables through the development of a new generation of cost-effective sensors and samplers, the integration of the aforementioned technologies within observing platforms and their deployment in large-scale demonstrations in European seas. The fundamental aim of the project will be to complement and expand current European observation tools and services, to obtain a collection of data at a much higher spatial resolution, temporal regularity and length than currently available at the European scale, and to further enable and democratise the monitoring of the marine environment to both traditional and non-traditional data users.

NAUTILOS is one of two projects included in the EU's efforts to support of the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy by supporting the demonstration of new and innovative technologies to measure the Essential Ocean Variables (EOV).

More information on the project can be found at: www.nautilus-h2020.eu.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main objectives of Task 7.5 “Animal-borne instruments” was to demonstrate the use of two animal tags with dissolved oxygen sensors on sharks, mobula rays and elephant seals. The present document is the final report of Task 7.5 and reports results of the work carried out by partners from M6 up to M57, illustrates further developments, issues encountered, solutions adopted and data exchange with the NAUTILOS data stream services.

Therefore, it is organised in 5 main sections:

- Chapter I: Introduction, provides a brief summary of the activities carried out in T7.5 from CEiiA, CNRS and IMAR;
- Chapter II: MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag demonstration report, contains details on demonstrations on Atlantic, Pacific and Indian Oceans, carried out by IMAR, with technical support from CEiiA;
- Chapter III: SRDL-CTD-Oxy animal tag animal tag demonstration report, contains details on demonstrations on the Southern Ocean, carried out by CNRS, with technical support from SMRU;
- Chapter IV: Ethical Considerations, reports considerations on some ethical aspects relevant to the activities described in this deliverable.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
ARGOS	Advanced Research and Global Observation Satellite
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CTD	Conductivity–temperature–depth
D	Deliverable
DO	Dissolved oxygen
DO	Dissolved Oxygen
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GA	Grant Agreement
GTR	Galvanic Time Release
HR	High Resolution
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
KI	Kerguelen Island
LR	Low Resolution
m	meter
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
PET	Polyethylene Terephthalate
PMMA	Methyl polymethacrylate
PV	Valdes Peninsula
SES	South Elephant Seals
SO	Southern Ocean
SRDL	Satellite related data loggers
TRL	Technology Readiness Levels
UA	University of Aveiro
UART	Universal Asynchronous Receiver-Transmitter
UI	User Interface

VHF	Very high frequency
WEEE	Waste from Electrical and Electronic Equipment
WP	Work Package

I. INTRODUCTION

The implementation of animal-borne tagging systems capable of in-situ monitoring of marine, their deep-sea habitats and essential ocean variable, enables not only for scientific and academic communities to more accurately understand these species' habitats, habitat use and understand the impacts of the human activities, but as also to identify the impacts and changes that these habitats face through high frequency multisensor concurrent data acquisition. The information collected from the instruments is relevant for comprehending migration routes, the interaction of the animals with their environment, habit use, interactions between different species together with other important parameters for the comprehension of the marine environment. The acquired knowledge is critical to support science-based species and habitat conservation measures to ensure the sustainable co-habitation between humans, their activities and resilient natural systems.

To augment the dataset that can be retrieved from seafaring animals, and simultaneously better inform about the animals' behavior and the surrounding habitat with a view to data sharing with the wider community, animal-borne tagging systems integrate sensors that provide geo referenced data, such as temperature, depth, salinity, bio-fluorescence, luminosity, animal behaviour and energy use (acceleration) and focal observations of behaviour and habitat (optical cameras). These sophisticated animal-borne systems are developed to integrate multiple sensors while remaining small and low-impact for the species to be tagged, aligning to the most advanced ethical and animal welfare guidelines currently in place. The most innovative component of the new animal-borne tag system is the dissolved oxygen sensor, enabling the seamless integration of this essential ocean variable with high-frequency data on animal behaviour, depth, temperature, light intensity, and bioluminescence, recorded directly as the tagged marine animals explore their essential habitats, often inaccessible to traditional manned oceanographic platforms.

Over the last decades, several studies based on measurements in-situ and modelling have clearly noted a decreasing trend in the concentration of dissolved oxygen in the oceans as a result of climate change. First, the solubility of oxygen decreases as the oceans warm. Second, warmer ocean waters are more stable, thereby slowing down the ocean circulation system and reducing the vertical mixing processes between water masses. The result is less oxygen transported from the oxygen-rich surface layer (in contact with air) into the deep ocean, where layers depleted in dissolved O₂ (oxygen minimum zones—OMZ) are expanding (Shaffer et al. 2009). In addition, the slowing down of the ocean's circulation system also results in a reduced supply of nutrients from the deep layers into the ocean surface. The low availability of nutrients in the surface layers causes the decline of phytoplankton biomass and diversity (i.e., oxygen producers) and hence, the level of oxygen at the surface is bound to decline further. Influenced both by physical and dynamical characteristics of water masses and biological production, dissolved O₂ proves to be a sensitive indicator of changes in properties of the marine environment. Despite the critical role of dissolved oxygen as a proxy for climate change related changes in the oceans, the future impact of its declining on marine life and ecosystems' health remains unclear and difficult to assess. A decrease in dissolved oxygen concentration could affect the biological activity of micro-organisms at depth and hence, generate perturbation in the functioning of ecosystems and accelerate changes in biogeochemical cycling. High performance predators like sharks, marlin and tuna, will have their available habitat compressed and reduced as a result of overall declining dissolved oxygen and growth and shallowing of OMZs, limiting access to prey and increasing their vulnerability to industrial fisheries (Vedor et al. 2021).

The integration of dissolved oxygen sensors into animal-borne multisensor tags offers a powerful tool to investigate critical but poorly understood aspects of animal ecology in relation to their environment. This includes behavioural responses to fluctuating oxygen concentrations and habitat preferences across dynamic oxscapes. Furthermore, deploying such sensors on deep-diving oceanic species presents a unique opportunity to leverage these "evolutionarily informed oceanographers" to collect high-resolution in-situ oceanographic data in a more cost-effective and spatially extensive manner than traditional ship-based surveys reliant on large, costly research vessels. These measurements will also contribute to better

understanding the distribution and density of the mesopelagic organisms within the water column by improving the information availability and resolution to feed the global predictive models such as “Spatial Ecosystem And Population Dynamics Model” (SEAPODYM). All these parameters will be sampled simultaneously with the in-situ oceanographic conditions to assess their influence on the vertical distribution of mesopelagic organisms.

Therefore, within the scope of the NAUTILOS project, an oxygen sensor of significant maturity was integrated into two field tested and proven non-invasive animal-borne tagging systems developed by CEiiA and SMRU, tested by IMAR on sharks and rays and CNRS on southern elephant seals in the scope of Task 7.5.

II. DEMONSTRATION REPORT | MAANTA NAUTILOS ANIMAL TAG

1. BACKGROUND

The tagging systems developed by CEiiA (MAANTA product line) are a set of tagging devices with the purpose of tracking marine animals while recording their behavioral, physiological and environmental conditions. They play a key role in marine conservation by helping research scientists relate an animal's behavior to its surrounding environment.

MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag is a novel and disruptive product developed in the scope of this project. The challenge relates to the integration of a dissolved oxygen sensor into a non-invasive animal-towed tagging system (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Non-invasive animal towed tagging system used for animals such as manta rays and sharks | MAANTA NAUTILOS.

Like other tagging devices in this product line, the MAANTA NAUTILOS platform is designed for depths up to 2,000 m (unfortunately for the NAUTILOS duration only the 1000m version is available - Appendix 2), ensuring recoverability while maintaining a minimal volume and thus reduced resistance force. This design focuses on the interference minimization with the target species leading to a least energy expenditure of the animal during deployment, and consequently to an improvement in data quality acquisition. Also, this kind of systems typically rely on transmitters/receivers devices to be able to be recovered. In the scope of this project, commercial Very High Frequency (VHF) radio and satellite transmitters were considered.

To reduce operating costs regarding the number of tagging missions, the MAANTA NAUTILOS was designed for easy replacement of its rechargeable battery and memory card. This allows the user to tag an animal at the same location where the device was recovered, eliminating the need to return to land for battery charging and data retrieval.

The MAANTA NAUTILUS electronics consists of a data logger along with a set of sensors described below:

- Environmental sensors:
 - Commercial pressure (depth) and Temperature sensors.

- Motion sensors:
 - Hall (velocity) - external paddle wheel with magnets embedded;
 - Accelerometer (Acceleration) - integrated in IMU;
 - Magnetometer and Gyroscope (Orientation) - integrated in IMU.

- External sensors:
 - Dissolved Oxygen sensor (Pico-O2-SUB from PyroScience).

The MAANTA NAUTILUS animal tag was developed for large sharks and mobula rays. Demonstration actions were planned for the following species:

- Chilean devil rays;
- Broad-nose sixgill sharks;
- Blue sharks.

Although the focus has been on the species referred above, MAANTA NAUTILUS tags can also be deployed on other species with similar behavior. This behavior shall be assessed in terms of operational requirements, mostly focused on:

- Maximum and nominal swimming speeds (stable up to 4 m/s);
- Maximum and nominal swimming depths (up to 2000 m);
- Shape and size of the target species (although not limitative, should allow for lasso-method deployment);
- Additional force resistance (Drag) caused on the target species (both platform and animal geometries were hydrodynamically assessed, and an additional Drag of +5% was set as the maximum allowable for operation, i.e. deployments were not recommended in juvenile individuals or small species where the additional drag would be higher than 5%);
- Typical motion patterns of the target species;
- Target species behavior with human interaction.

Other species where the MAANTA NAUTILUS can be deployed, but not limited to are:

- Mako sharks;
- Basking sharks;
- Hammerhead sharks;
- Tiger sharks;
- Whale sharks.

The development of MAANTA NAUTILUS posed a major challenge in terms of mechanical and electronics, not considered to be extensively detailed in the following chapters. However, major challenges faced and solved are described on Appendix 2.

2. DEMONSTRATION PLAN

As expected within the scope of NAUTILUS Grant Agreement, the plan for demonstration of MAANTA NAUTILUS (the non-invasive animal tagging system integrated with a dissolved oxygen sensor), was to center demonstrations on three representative megafauna species in the Atlantic Ocean and thus to cover various geographical areas and depths, representing contrasting ecologies, behaviors and habitat use the following species were initially planned to be tagged:

- Devil rays: broader (circa 20 km²) and deep (from 0 to 1800m, typically down to 600m) ocean coverage
- Bluntnose sixgill shark: deeper depths (circa 150m daytime to 1200m at night) in winter months but lower area covered (5 km²)
- Blue shark: shallower depths (circa up to 1400m, typically 0-300m) in summer months but more extensive coverage (50 km²) of ocean area

This objective was achieved, as it will be described later, however a major breakthrough was possible with the new opportunities that arose along the course of the project, where IMAR redesigned the initial objectives based on opportunistic events to include:

- Three additional species:
 - Whale shark *Rhincodon typus*
 - Shortfin mako shark *Isurus oxyrinchus*
 - Ragged tooth sand tiger shark *Odontaspis ferox*
- Two new locations:
 - Pacific Ocean
 - Indian Ocean

Animal-borne deployments depend on the availability of the tags, time of year, weather conditions, and as expected all previous considerations were faced during the scope of the project with an addition for some maintenance activities due to unexpected bites from animals. To better understand the course of the demonstration activities, all deployments are described, per location, along the next chapters of this document.

Table 1 summarises the MAANTA NAUTILUS tag deployments conducted across three ocean basins and six elasmobranch species, detailed in the following sections, per deployment location (per Ocean).

Table 1: MAANTA NAUTILOS deployments in the Atlantic, Pacific and Indian Ocean (drop test deployments not listed).

MISSION ID	TAG ID	DATE and TIME	SPECIES	COMMON NAME	MAXIMUM DEPHT (m)	DEPLOYMENT DURATION (h)	TIME to TAG RECOVERY (h)	LOCATION (Ocean)
20240429230000-SG-01	LITE6b306470	2024/04/29 04:33:00	<i>H.griseus</i>	Bluntnose sixgill shark	486.15	47.83	84.17	Atlantic
20240626130000-MS-01	LITE6b306470	2024/06/26 15:30:00	<i>I. oxyrhincus</i>	Shortfin mako shark	138.42	30.70	72.00	Atlantic
20240627120000-BS-01	LITE6142647f	2024/06/27 18:27:00	<i>P. glauca</i>	Blue shark	282.08	20.86	67.37	Atlantic
20240812120000-MB-01	LITE6143647e	2024/08/12 13:30:00	<i>M.tarapacana</i>	Chilean devil ray	1075.91	31.31	90.70	Atlantic
20240812120000-MB-02	LITE6142647b	2024/08/12 14:10:00	<i>M.tarapacana</i>	Chilean devil ray	205.93	15.49	45.95	Atlantic
20240816130000-WS-01	LITE6142647b	2024/08/16 14:41:00	<i>R.typus</i>	Whale shark	15.45	0.09	65.75	Atlantic
20240819110000-WS-02	LITE6143647e	2024/08/19 11:17:00	<i>R.typus</i>	Whale shark	134.76	3.60	27.60	Atlantic
20240819150000-WS-03	LITE6142647b	2024/08/19 11:40:00	<i>R.typus</i>	Whale shark	1281.8	53.88	73.15	Atlantic
20240821120000-WS-04	LITE6143647e	2024/08/21 13:15:00	<i>R.typus</i>	Whale shark	785.81	18.30	67.83	Atlantic
20240825123000-MB-03	LITE6142647b	2024/08/25 15:27:00	<i>M.tarapacana</i>	Chilean devil ray	1244.16	46.90	286.78	Atlantic
20240828120000-MB-04	LITE6143647e	2024/08/28 14:05:00	<i>M.tarapacana</i>	Chilean devil ray	219.24	31.30	234.67	Atlantic
20240909150000-BS-02	LITE6142647b	2024/09/09 15:20:00	<i>P. glauca</i>	Blue shark	92.58	1.69	2.17	Atlantic

20240909150000-BS-03	LITE6143647e	2024/09/09 15:40:00	<i>P. glauca</i>	Blue shark	217.5	0.17	1.17	Atlantic
20240909170900-BS-04	LITE6143647e	2024/09/09 17:09:00	<i>P. glauca</i>	Blue shark	20.34	0.16	0.20	Atlantic
20240911120000-BS-05	LITE6142647b	2024/09/11 13:20:00	<i>P. glauca</i>	Blue shark	678.99	23.02	70.47	Atlantic
20240911120000-BS-06	LITE6143647e	2024/09/11 13:30:00	<i>P. glauca</i>	Blue shark	619.58	15.00	71.00	Atlantic
20240919140000-BS-07	LITE6143647e	2024/09/19 15:00:00	<i>P. glauca</i>	Blue shark	806.11	25.44	67.77	Atlantic
20250205123000-HS-01	LITE6143647e	2025/02/05 08:30:00	<i>H. sapiens</i>	Human	65	2.00	2.00	Pacific
20250523000100-SG-02	LITE6143647e	2025/05/23 05:08:00	<i>H. griseus</i>	Bluntnose sixgill shark	173.5	2.5	61.46	Atlantic
20250529030001-SG-03	LITE6143647e	2025/05/29 02:22:00	<i>H. griseus</i>	Bluntnose sixgill shark	720	25.80	69.14	Atlantic
20250616070000-WS-04	LITE6142647b	2025/06/16 09:05:00	<i>R. typus</i>	Whale shark	193	21.62	23.03	Indian
20250618070000-WS-05	LITE6142647b	2025/06/18 07:58:00	<i>R. typus</i>	Whale shark	226	32.01	47.52	Indian
20250621070000-WS-06	LITE6146647e	2025/06/21 07:46:00	<i>R. typus</i>	Whale shark	5	0.1	23.75	Indian
20250622070000-WS-07	LITE6142647b	2025/06/22 09:05:00	<i>R. typus</i>	Whale shark	195	30.1	46.52	Indian
GRANDE TOTAL						479.9	1602.2	

3. DEMONSTRATIONS – ATLANTIC OCEAN (PORTUGAL – AZORES ARCHIPELAGO)

- **Specific Objectives**

The main goal with the Atlantic Ocean deployments was to validate MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag behaviour operation in the open sea. Tagging activities were limited due to initial technical challenges until 2024 (as reported in Appendix 2), leaving much less time than originally anticipated. Besides the product testing, also IMAR's objective was to characterize their oxygen uptake, swimming kinematics, and diving behavior, since these data are crucial for revealing how these species manage hypoxic conditions and move across marine oxyscapes, optimize energy expenditure during long, deep dives, and maintain physiological performance under the extreme pressures of the abyss.

- **Platform involved**

For all Atlantic Ocean deployments, IMAR used MAANTA NAUTILOS with the following serial numbers LITE6b306470; LITE6142647f; LITE6142647b and LITE6143647e.

- **Deployment configuration**

MAANTA NAUTILOS tags were attached to the animals (Figure 2) using harness around the dorsal fin (large mature and large immature whale sharks) or around the body (six-gill shark, short-fin-mako shark, blue shark, small immature whale shark).

Figure 2: Whale shark (top) and blue shark (bottom) tagged with the MAANTA NAUTILOS tag in the Azores, Portugal. Photos: ImageDOP-OKEANOS-UAc.

The mission duration for these specific activities was planned for 24 to 48 hours, meaning the maximum expected duration of recorded data was 48 hours. However, the actual deployment times (i.e., the duration the equipment remained in the water) were variable. This variability was mainly due to whether a migrating animal was tagged, due to technical issues that made it difficult to re-establish communication with the equipment at sea or premature release.

- **Location**

The three main locations in the Azores were: Faial-Pico Channel; Condor Bank and Princess Alice Bank. The Faial-Pico Channel, a narrow stretch of water between Faial and Pico islands, is known for its rich marine biodiversity, attracting whale watchers and divers. The southwest, Condor Bank, an underwater seamount, generates nutrient-rich upwellings, supporting a variety of fish and marine life. Further south, Princess Alice Bank, another submerged seamount, is renowned for its diverse ecosystems, including manta rays, sharks, and vibrant fish populations, both banks focal for marine research and conservation. These three areas represent some of the most ecologically rich regions in the Azores, attracting marine researchers and ecotourists (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Geographic location of the three deployment sites in the Azores, Portugal.

- **Period of animal tagging activities**

From April 2024 until the end of the project (June 2025), the IMAR team conducted various missions to tag different species in the Faial Island surroundings as described in Table 1.

- **Maintenance, events/issues occurred and actions taken**

MAANTA NAUTILOS RECOVERY

All the MAANTA NAUTILOS tags were successfully recovered, demonstrating a 100% recovery rate. As mentioned before and reported on Appendix 2, the product includes syntactic foams, i.e. buoyant halves, developed to accommodate all payload while ensuring the optimal hydrodynamics and stability during deployments. Their development is critical as it defines the behavior of MAANTA NAUTILOS during operation (attached to the animal) and aims to ensure the tag will be retrieved after deployment. i.e. the platform shall in any event be able to return to its equilibrium position (antennas facing upwards) while floating at the surface (Figure 4), otherwise it won't communicate through the antennas (satellite or VHF radio) and won't be recovered. Furthermore, they are also developed giving special attention to where the waterline is while the platform is at the surface, since the satellite sensor will only activate after the wet-dry switch detects the tag is floating at the surface.

The 100% rate is a specific feature from all MAANTA products. Once again, in the scope of NAUTILOS deployments this was confirmed. Despite being related to the product concept this is also a result of the effort from the IMAR team (and other partners) during recovering missions.

Figure 4: Recovery of the floating (red) MAANTA NAUTILOS tag off the North coast of Faial Island after a deployment in a bluntnose sixgill shark.

In general, tag recovery was accomplished within one 8-hours mission. This is mainly applicable for short-term 24-hour deployments because this limits the potential maximum travelling distance of animals (in case tagging occurs on an animal on migration). From all the Atlantic Ocean deployments, two recovery missions exceed 8 hours.

One of them occurred in April 2024. As previously explained, MAANTA NAUTILOS tags rely on satellite and VHF radio transmitters for localization and recovery. In the scope of this project, commercial Very High Frequency (VHF) radio and satellite transmitters were considered. For an unknown reason ARGOS satellite transmitter did not activate and the MAANTA tag was drifting for approximately 36h after being released from the shark until the IMAR team was able to detect the VHF radio signal for the first time from elevated points around the Faial Island. After detecting the VHF signal, this issue was mitigated by determining the MAANTA NAUTILOS location through triangulation, using azimuths from multiple elevated fixed points (e.g., hilltops and mountaintops) via VHF radio direction finding (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Map of the reference coordinates used for triangulate the VHF radio signals and locate the MAANTA NAUTILOS tag in the North shore of Faial Island, Azores, Portugal.

Also, in 25th and 28th of August 2024 IMAR team tagged two Chilean devil rays, and both travelled southward after they were tagged. After 48h deployment, the MAANTA tags released and sent the tags' location at 75 and 115 nautical miles distance from the Faial Island. The deployment site, Princess Alice bank, is 46 nautical miles NNW off Faial Island. Due to the unfavorable weather conditions, during the following week, IMAR team was forced to postpone the recovery mission to retrieve the tags. After waiting for almost a week, the tags drifted even further from Faial to the distances of 95 and 135 nautical miles. IMAR's team sought sailing boats with extended autonomy capable of navigating such distances. However, since the weather was still not ideal for sailing, the captains did not want to risk such a long mission under limiting weather conditions. We then turned to the Portuguese Navy ship for help. The oceanic patrol vessel "NRP Figueira da Foz" was in the region to monitor the sea around the Azores and agreed to help with the recovery mission. By the time we sailed to the tag location further away, the MAANTA tag was 175 nautical miles away from the Faial is (Figure 6).

Figure 6: NAUTILOS social media post highlighting the longest mission ever to recovery a tag by the IMAR team, with support from the Portuguese Navy. The story was reported by the TV channel RTP Azores.

MAANTA NAUTILOS MAINTENANCE

MAANTA NAUTILOS is a scientific instrument that requires careful handling to ensure its proper functioning. As part of the NAUTILOS project, CEiA provided IMAR with a quick maintenance guide covering several important aspects in order to support users in achieving the best results. This guide outlines essential best practices for handling, storage, cleaning, and transport, which are critical to prevent system failures and to ensure consistent data quality.

Despite the implementation of these good practices, the recovery of MAANTA NAUTILOS tags from multiple deployments enabled the verification of various post-release effects. These findings underscore the importance of continuous inspection and post-deployment analysis to identify potential improvements in both operational procedures and equipment robustness.

In some cases, bite marks from the blue sharks were observed on the foam components (Figure 7). These events likely occur after the tag is released and begins floating/driftng at the surface - the sharks appear to follow the tag as it ascends and subsequently bite it.

Figure 7: MAANTA NAUTILOS tag's foam after some deployments in blue sharks in the Azores. The white spots are the bite marks.

Another potential consequence during this drifting phase is the heavy encrustation of the foam by sessile invertebrates or covered by small crabs or zooplankton (Figure 8). Among the various post-deployment incidents, Figure 9 highlights an interaction with a triggerfish that resulted in the destruction of the tag's dissolved oxygen sensor protective cage and optical fiber, rendering the sensor inoperative. The tag was later returned to CEiIA for maintenance.

Figure 8: MAANTA NAUTILOS tag fully covered by invertebrates after ca. 48h drifting in the North shore of Faial Island, Azores, Portugal.

Figure 9: Triggerfish bite while the MAANTA NAUTILOS was drifting after being released in the vicinity of Princess Alice bank, 46 nautical miles SW off Faial Island.

Also, after prolonged use in the marine environment, components such as containers, lids, and penetrators may show signs of corrosion (Figure 10). Similar deterioration may appear on the paddle wheel and buoyant halves. To ensure continued manufacturer support, IMAR periodically reported the condition of the equipment, especially during periods of active use. This information was essential to assess the need for maintenance and to ensure reliable operation.

Figure 10: MAANTA NAUTILOS containers with the first signal of corrosion, reported by IMAR.

- **Data recovery, analysis and post processing**

DATA RECOVERY AND SHARING

The data from all deployments (Table 1) was successfully retrieved from the LITE units. All the retrieved raw data was uploaded in the NAUTILOS cloud drive (Figure 11). After data quality check, the operational data was uploaded by IMAR to the NAUTILOS FTP server (Figure 12) and, thus, included in the NAUTILOS ERDDAP™ repository (according to the project data sharing scheme made by ETT - Deliverables 8.3 and 8.4).

Figure 11: Screenshots from the NAUTILOS/CEiia's cloud drive showing the data folders from laboratory experiments (left) and field tests (right) conducted.

Figure 12: FTP folder organization for MAANTA NAUTILOS: scheme (left); real (right).

For each deployment, a folder should be created in the deployment institution's folder as shown in Figure 13. Each subfolder must be created for each deployment with a standard nomenclature as described in Figure X, including a reference for the animal type abbreviation is described in the Table 2.

Figure 13: Deployment folder naming.

Table 2: Animal type abbreviation reference for MAANTA NAUTILOS standard nomenclature.

Abbreviation	Animal type	GA Expected/Extra
SG	sixgill shark	Extra
MS	mako shark	Extra
BS	blue shark	Expected
MB	mobula ray	Expected
WS	whale shark	Expected

In order to properly organize files for data sharing purposes (WP9), MAANTA NAUTILOS users need to convert and adapt original files, replacing file naming (Figure 14) and, in the case of the metadata file, introducing the new variables (Figure 15).

Figure 14: File naming structure.

Figure 15: Conversion scheme for the different deployment files.

Each FTP subfolder (per deployment) has three types of files, complying with the expected structure:

- data file - the data file (csv) is generated automatically (based on the mission configuration) and contains the data from each sensor at the defined rate;
- metadata file - based on the official NAUTILOS metadata file provided by ETT (Deliverable 1.12) with the addition of specific properties related to the deployment (Figure 16);
- location file - generated by the CLS Argos platform or satellite transmitter manufacturer's software, once the "Lite Tag" (electronics) does not have a position tracker. Since the animal is almost always below the water surface, it is difficult to obtain satellite positions, since the type of tag used requires a minimal time at surface and satellites passing over the area to transmit the positions to the satellite system. Deployment and recovery positions can be entered manually, and the file structure should have the format described in Figure 17 (columns are comma-separated).

Figure 16: Additional fields (and corresponding description) of MAANTA NAUTILOS metadata file.

Figure 17: Location file with deployment/recovery positions.

Following some alignment meetings between CEiiA, ETT and IMAR (Figure 18), data stored in FTP were afterwards uploaded by ETT to ERDDAP™ and by CNR-ISTI to NAUTILOS Data Portal, as presented in the deliverable 5.8. Data are available on ERDDAP™ at the following links:

- data: https://data-nautilus-h2020.eu/erddap/tabledap/animal_tag_ceiia_data.html
- metadata: https://data-nautilus-h2020.eu/erddap/tabledap/animal_tag_ceiia_metadata.html
- data portal: <https://nautilus-h2020.eu/data-portal/>

Figure 18: Meeting between CEiiA, IMAR and ETT teams to discuss data upload to ERDDAP™ and NAUTILOS Data Portal. On the left side, NOAA's ERDDAP™ repository screenshot displaying the MAANTA NAUTILOS operational data.

Data plotting was discussed mainly with IMAR and several options were discussed. The final decision (Figure 19) on how to represent the animal tag data on the NAUTILOS data portal managed by CNR-ISTI includes the following items:

- deployment position represented by a green circle;
- recovery position represented by a red circle;
- a dotted line connecting the two points, so that it is clear that this is not the real animal route;
- marker that shows mission information when pressed;
- pressing the line between the points triggers a pop-up that shows the relation between some of the measured properties (on a graph): depth vs time; temperature vs depth; oxygen (concentration) vs depth and oxygen (air saturation) vs depth.

Figure 19: NAUTILOS data portal displaying MAANTA NAUTILOS data, for a specific mission.

DATA ANALYSIS

After numerous deployments, reported previously, a substantial amount of interesting and representative data was collected, reflecting extended periods of MAANTA NAUTILOS operation at sea. While part of this dataset displays high quality and scientific value data, for other parts some of the dissolved oxygen (DO) measurements fell outside the expected range and required further review. These anomalies and post processing techniques will be addressed in more detail in the post-processing chapter.

Below are two examples of raw data collected involving different species to illustrate the potential of the collected data and the insights it can provide.

- BLUNTNOSE SIXGILL SHARK | Raw data example

The first animal tagged with the NAUTILOS MAANTA tag was a bluntnose sixgill shark, tagged in the early hours of June 29th 2024, using the LITE6b36470. The measured water temperature and DO concentration were relatively stable and within expected values for the region and the depth used by the tagged shark (Figure 20).

Figure 20: Depth, temperature and oxygen concentration profiles from bluntnose sixgill shark (*Hexanchus griseus*, SG-01) deployment with the LITE6b36470 in the Faial-Pico Island channel.

- CHILEAN DEVIL RAY | Raw data example

The first-ever deployment on a Chilean devil ray yielded a rich and novel dataset, including an incursion to the bathyal zone, deeper than one kilometer. The DO data range was within the expected values for the region and time of the year (Figure 21).

Figure 21: Depth, temperature and oxygen concentration profiles from a Chilean devil ray (*Mobula tarapacana*, MB-01) deployment with the LITE 6143647e at the Princesa Alice bank, 46 nautical miles SW off Faial island.

While processing data (mainly acquired from the summer season of 2024), and facing the fact that some dissolved oxygen (DO) values fell outside the expected range, a thorough investigation was initiated by both IMAR and CEiiA (involving also PYRO SCIENCE - DO sensor supplier), leading to the identification of two main contributing factors: insufficient water circulation over the pressure/temperature sensor membrane due to the foam's internal geometry and the absence of post-shipping calibration of the optical sensor caps, which were previously assumed to be all factory-calibrated after initial WP6 tests at HCMR (described in the Chapter V of deliverable 6.1) and initial field data acquisitions in April 2024 (Appendix 4). For this reason, when new units were sent in 2024, CEiiA and IMAR assumed them to be factory calibrated and ready for use, and tagging efforts resumed immediately, targeting blue sharks, shortfin mako sharks, and Chilean devil rays, with occasional opportunistic deployments on whale sharks to increase the amplitude of tagged organisms and compensate previous delays. During this highly intensive tagging period, the tags were deployed and recovered multiple times to maximise utilisation across available weather windows. However, after one of the DO sensor caps sustained damage from a triggerfish, the corresponding unit was required to be returned to CEiiA for cap replacement. This operational pause facilitated a more comprehensive examination of the collected datasets, leading to the generation of the first DO profiles. Initial analysis disclosed several significant outliers and inconsistencies in the DO measurements, thereby prompting additional investigation. To evaluate sensor accuracy and performance, the IMAR team executed a series of laboratory experiments, which included comparisons of both LITE units with a calibrated third-party optical DO sensor and CTD casts to verify environmental baselines and identify potential sources of error (Appendix 5).

To address the hydrodynamic issue, the IMAR team performed a mechanical assessment of the MAANTA NAUTILUS tag's foam structure and proposed a minor modification: the removal of a small section of foam in front of the sensor membrane to create a dedicated tunnel. This redesign aimed to improve water flow and ensure direct contact between ambient water and the sensing surface. Stability simulations were conducted to evaluate the impact of the modification on buoyancy and waterline; results showed negligible effects. The CEiiA team validated the proposed solution using computational fluid dynamics (CFD) modelling, confirming both the safety of the alteration and identifying the optimal volume and

location of foam to be removed (Figure 22). Following CEiiA's approval, IMAR manually implemented engineering modifications to the tag housing to enhance sensor exposure to ambient water, particularly during dynamic vertical movements and tested the improved configuration for enhanced performance.

Figure 22: Original foam design (top), foam removal location approved by the CEiiA team (middle) and manual modification performed by the IMAR team (bottom). Note: The sensor diaphragm membrane is now exposed to the water.

In parallel, facing the “apparent” absent calibration issue, several interactions between CEiiA and PYRO SCIENCE happen and both teams (IMAR and CEiiA) collaborated closely to establish and implement appropriate calibration protocols, conducting multiple calibration sessions at the University of Aveiro and the University of the Azores (Figure 23).

Figure 23: IMAR - First oxygen sensor calibration by IMAR team with CEiiA support (09/01/2025).

Once again (as throughout the project; Appendix 4 and 5) IMAR performed controlled laboratory tests with the LITE units and a reference multiparameter (Figure 24), as also descent and ascent data acquisition simultaneously with MAANTA NAUTILOS tags and a conductivity, temperature, and depth (CTD) at the

sea. New drop tests were conducted to assess the effectiveness of the modification and LITE6143647e unit calibration on 2025/01/09 (Figure 25). New CTD drops with foams showed IMAR an acceptable temperature deviation of about 1.5°C (in accordance with sensor resolution by the manufacturer) as Table 3 shows.

Figure 24: Oxygen sensor calibration at IMAR and the reference sensor considered for the calibration process (09/01/2025)

Figure 25: Simultaneous ca. 100m depth cast (drop 1, left; drop 2, right) of CTD along with the LITE6143647e, after foam modification and dissolved oxygen calibration, showing the dissolved oxygen concentration (umol/L) per depth from December 2024 in the Azores, Portugal (2025/01/09).

Table 3: Summary of the dissolved oxygen concentration (umol/L), temperature (°C) and depth (m) from the field comparison on 2025/01/17. The results show the difference (delta) between LITE6143647e and the CTD readings.

DROP 01	delta LITE - CTD		
	O2 (umol/L)	Temp (°C)	Depth (m)
mean	-16.70	-1.52	-0.49
media	-16.92	-1.54	0.39
sd	1.94	0.12	13.80
ci (0.05)	0.38	0.02	2.72
DROP 02	delta LITE - CTD		
	O2 (umol/L)	Temp (°C)	Depth (m)
mean	-16.26	-1.53	-2.16
media	-16.29	-1.54	-2.24
sd	0.83	0.05	1.24
ci (0.05)	0.25	0.01	0.38

These findings highlighted dissolved oxygen parameter sensitivity and above all the need for systematic calibration procedures for all new optical sensor caps (and also probably, maintenance calibration activities to be assessed during the expected use after the project), a requirement that is not clearly evidenced by the supplier. While these issues were not initially foreseeable, they were thoroughly investigated and resolved through a combination of laboratory testing, engineering adaptations, and procedural updates. This represents a significant technical outcome and for this reason described in the present report, as it demonstrates the CEiiA and IMAR team’s ability to overcome unexpected challenges through intensive problem-solving and additional effort. However, this troubleshooting process's complexity and time delayed animal-borne deployments, reducing the expected time available for deployments however without consequences as several good data was acquired and made available. Also, these measures significantly improved the reliability of the DO measurements and restored confidence in the sensor performance, still in time for additional deployments still during NAUTILOS timeline. As a result, improved protocols are being applied to all ongoing and future tagging efforts. The lessons learned throughout this process are expected to increase the robustness of biologging deployments and ensure consistent data quality across the remaining project timeline.

DATA - POST PROCESSING

As mentioned before, data processing was necessary as some of the dissolved oxygen (DO) measurements fell outside the expected range and required further review. As such, IMAR made an extra effort (not expected in the scope of the present grant agreement) to develop data processing techniques within the framework of a Master’s thesis at the University of the Azores, aiming to correct and validate the data collected under the NAUTILOS project.

In order to address a persistent but not consistent bias identified in the dissolved oxygen (DO) data obtained from the LITE tag sensor, an empirical correction based on linear regression relative to a reference data source—Copernicus Ocean Reanalysis—was implemented. The LITE DO concentrations were systematically compared with the Copernicus modelled DO data (Figure 26), alongside simultaneous temperature measurements (Figure 27), to validate the sensor outputs under varying environmental conditions rigorously.

Figure 26: Dissolved oxygen concentration profiles (blue, Tag) from Chilean devil ray (*Mobula tarapacana*, MB-01) tagged with LITE 6143647e (left) and bluntnose sixgill shark (*Hexanchus griseus*, SG-01) tagged with LITE6b36470 (right) in direct comparison with the Copernicus Ocean Reanalysis (red, Model).

Figure 27: Temperature profiles (blue, Tag) from Chilean devil ray (*Mobula tarapacana*, MB-01) tagged with LITE 6143647e (left) and bluntnose sixgill shark (*Hexanchus griseus*, SG-01) tagged with LITE6b36470 (right) in direct comparison with the Copernicus Ocean Reanalysis (red, Model).

This correction model was developed using concurrent observations to quantify and correct both offset and gain discrepancies in the sensor readings, assuming a stable linear relationship between the in-situ optode measurements and the modelled data. Such a relationship is consistent with optode intercalibration principles documented in previous studies (Bittig et al., 2018; Emerson et al., 2018). Validation involved statistical assessments of correlation, residual errors, and detection of systematic deviations across different temperature and pressure ranges to ensure robust performance of the corrected dataset. These steps were critical to enhancing data reliability and comparability. They enabled the integration of biologging DO data with large-scale oceanographic reanalysis products and facilitated subsequent ecological and biogeochemical analyses.

Prior to applying the regression correction, the tag data underwent a rigorous two-stage quality control process to remove outliers. Initially, a locally estimated scatterplot smoothing (LOESS) function was independently fitted to temperature and dissolved oxygen (DO) observations to capture expected vertical profiles. Residuals from these fits were calculated, and any values deviating beyond ± 1 standard deviation from the LOESS curve were excluded as outliers. Following this filtering, DO and temperature measurements from both the LITE tag and Copernicus reference datasets were aggregated into matching

10-meter depth bins. A linear regression model was then fitted to quantify the relationship between the datasets and derive a correction factor. This factor was applied to the raw tag data across the depth range to normalize and correct systematic discrepancies.

To facilitate direct comparison and interpretation, both the corrected tag data and the Copernicus model outputs were jointly normalized using the shared minimum and maximum DO concentrations from the combined dataset. This min-max scaling transformed DO values into a relative percentage scale (0–100%), preserving the natural depth-dependent variability while allowing consistent comparison across different instruments and temporal contexts (Figure 28 and Figure 29).

This post-processing step led to an update of the metadata (i.e., input file to ETT), through the inclusion of a quality status (QA) column indicating the type of processing applied, for example, “none,” “outlier removal,” or “advanced post-processing techniques” (Figure 16). Corrected data was made available on ERDDAP, following previously mentioned data sharing protocol defined for NAUTILOS project.

Figure 28: Regression-corrected and normalized relative Dissolved Oxygen (DO%, red) profiles from Chilean devil ray (*Mobula tarapacana*, MB-01) (left) and bluntnose sixgill Shark (*Hexanchus griseus*, SG-01) (right) Compared with Copernicus Ocean Reanalysis reference data (blue).

Figure 29: Regression-corrected and normalized relative temperature (°C; red) profiles from Chilean devil ray (*Mobula tarapacana*, MB-01) (left) and bluntnose sixgill Shark (*Hexanchus griseus*, SG-01) (right) compared with Copernicus Ocean Reanalysis reference data (blue).

DATA COMPARISON - RAW AND POST-PROCESSED

To illustrate the impact of data filtering on dissolved oxygen (DO) measurements, we present two-panel plots for two individual bluntnose sixgill sharks (Figure 30). In each panel, the first graph compares the raw and filtered DO profiles, with the filtered data obtained using an interquartile range (IQR)-based outlier removal method. The second graph displays only the values classified as outliers, highlighting their distribution across depth and time. This approach allows for a clear visualisation of the filtering effect and supports the quality control process applied to biological data.

Figure 30: DO profiles for a bluntnose sixgill shark: comparison between raw and IQR-filtered data (left). Filtering was based on the interquartile range method, applied to depth-binned values.

Outlier values removed from the DO datasets of the same individual (right), showing the distribution of outliers identified during the IQR-based filtering process. These points were excluded from subsequent analyses to ensure data quality.

4. DEMONSTRATIONS – PACIFIC OCEAN (COLOMBIA – MALPELO ISLAND)

- **Specific Objectives**

Pacific Ocean demonstrations were not initially foreseen within the scope of the NAUTILOS project; however, this new opportunity emerged during the course of the project, enabling an expansion of MAANTA NAUTILOS demonstrations. The mission was planned to tag the ragged tooth sand tiger shark (*Odontaspis ferox*) with MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag with dissolved oxygen sensor and Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) for the first time in the Pacific Ocean and Worldwide (IMAR Team in Figure 31).

- **Platform involved**

For the Pacific Ocean deployments, IMAR used MAANTA NAUTILOS with the following serial number LITE6143647e.

- **Deployment configuration**

Considering the species to tag, MAANTA NAUTILOS tags were intended to be deployed by towing with both harnesses and two types of customized clamps. Mission duration for these specific activities was planned for 24 hours, since it was the first use in a new species and ocean basin.

Figure 31: IMAR team, Jorge Fontes (left) and Bruno Macena (right), showing the MAANTA NAUILOS tag in Malpelo Island, Colombia.

- **Location**

Malpelo Fauna and Flora Sanctuary (<https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/1216/>; Figure 32) was the location selected for Pacific Ocean demonstrations. Malpelo Island is a large marine protected area around 500 km off Colombia's Pacific Coast. This vast marine park, the largest no-fishing zone in the Eastern Tropical Pacific, provides a critical habitat for internationally threatened marine species, and is a major source of nutrients resulting in large aggregations of marine biodiversity. The main objective was to tag a deep water shark species, the ragged tooth sand tiger shark (Figure 33), uncommonly found at ca. 60 m depth in a specific site called Bajo del Monstruo, located in the North shore of Malpelo island.

Figure 32: Geographical location of the Malpelo Island, Colombia. Inset shows a close up of the Malpelo Island.

- **Period of occurrence**

IMAR team (Figure 31) participated in an international mission from 28th February to 12th March partially supported also by the Fundación Malpelo y Otros Ecosistemas Marinos, managed by the executive director Sandra Bessudo, who invited the IMAR team to collaborate with their study on the ecology of the shark species and demonstrate this European technology developed by the NAUTILOS project to researchers from South America.

- **Data recovery**

Efforts to tag the deep-water shark were hindered by its specific behavior and anatomical features. As this was the IMAR team's first encounter with the species, a comprehensive understanding of its morphology was essential to devise a safe attachment protocol and to instruct technical closed-circuit rebreather divers, capable of exceeding 60 m depths and extended bottom times, in the deployment procedure. Operationally, only one tagging attempt could be made per day, since deep rebreather dives require considerably longer decompression and surface recovery periods than conventional open-circuit scuba, limited to maximum 40 m depth. Although direct tagging was not achieved, the MAANTA NAUTILOS tag remained active throughout the dive trials, producing two complete dissolved-oxygen profiles during the divers' descent and ascent. One of the two datasets collected from the MAANTA NAUTILOS tag carried by the technical rebreather diver during the deployment attempt (Figure 33) in Malpelo Island is shown in the Figure 34.

Figure 33: Ragged tooth sand tiger shark (top) tagging attempt (bottom) at 60 m depth, in Malpelo Island, Colombia. Photos: Fundación Malpelo y Otros Ecosistemas.

Although the elusive nature of this species prevented successful tagging, dissolved oxygen profile data were collected in a minimum oxygen zone, offering an environmental contrast to the oxygen-rich waters of the Azores.

The data from all deployments (Table 1) was successfully retrieved from the LITE units. As for the Atlantic Ocean, all the retrieved raw data was uploaded in the NAUTILUS cloud drive (Figure 11). After data quality check, the operational data was uploaded by IMAR to the NAUTILUS FTP server (Figure 12) and, thus, included in the NAUTILUS ERDDAP™ repository (according to the project data sharing scheme made by ETT - Deliverables 8.3 and 8.4).

Figure 34: Dissolved oxygen (DO) profiles of the rebreather diver carrying the MAANTA NAUTILUS tag during the deep water shark tagging attempt in Malpelo Island, Colombia. a) DO air saturation and b) concentration along the entire dive, c) dive depth and temperature profiles and d) DO concentration depth profile.

5. DEMONSTRATIONS – INDIAN OCEAN (INDONESIA – SALEH BAY)

- **Specific Objectives**

Indian Ocean demonstrations were not initially foreseen within the scope of the NAUTILOS project; however, this new opportunity emerged during the course of the project, enabling an expansion of MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag demonstrations. The mission was planned to tag juvenile whale sharks for the first time with a dissolved oxygen sensor in the indopacific ocean.

- **Platform/equipment involved**

For the Indian Ocean deployments, IMAR used MAANTA NAUTILOS tag with the following serial number LITE6143647e.

- **Deployment configuration**

Considering the species to tag, MAANTA NAUTILOS tags were intended to be deployed by towing with harnesses. Mission duration for these specific activities was planned for 24 to 48 hours, since the whale sharks are known to stay close to the aggregation area for a long time.

Considering past issues with calibration, preliminary tests were conducted by the IMAR team. A dissolved oxygen sensor field test comparison test was conducted on 06/05/2025. For this test, the two MAANTA NAUTILOS tags (LITE6143647e and LITE6142647b) were casted attached to the CTD fully assembled and with the LITE units only (without the foam) to ultimately compare the performance of the DO sensors within and without the modified foam (Figure 35). Results presented on Figure 36 and Figure 37 show the dissolved oxygen profiles from two LITE units and the CTD and Table 4 presents the difference between the LITE readings and the CTD.

Figure 35: Two fully assembled MAANTA NAUTILOS tags containing the units LITE6143647e and LITE6142647b attached to the CTD for a drop test in the Azores, Portugal.

Figure 36: Simultaneous ca. 400m depth cast of CTD and the LITE6143647e and LITE6142647b, after calibration and foam modification, showing the dissolved oxygen concentration (umol/L) from May 2025, in the Azores, Portugal. Drop 1.1 and 1.2 are using the MAANTA NAUTILOS tag fully assembled (top panel) and the Drop 2.1 and 2.2 are using only the LITE containers (bottom panel).

Figure 37: Simultaneous ca. 400 m depth cast of CTD and the LITE6143647e and LITE6142647b, after calibration and foam modification, showing the water temperature (°C) from May 2025, in the Azores, Portugal. Drop 1.1 and 1.2 are using the MAANTA NAUTILOS tag fully assembled (top panel) and the Drop 2.1 and 2.2 are using only the LITE containers (bottom panel).

Table 4: Summary of the depth (m), dissolved oxygen concentration (umol/L) and temperature (°C) differences of the LITE units from the CTD on 2025/05/06.

	LITE614264B		LITE614364E	
	mean	sd	mean	sd
Depth	-2.33	3.75	-8.09	7.84
O2	-28.82	6.13	-22.69	3.56
Temperature	-2.19	0.12	-1.58	0.16

- **Location**

Saleh Bay is a large, semi-enclosed bay located on the northern coast of Sumbawa Island, Indonesia (Figure 38). Encompassing approximately 1,459 km², it is bordered by the Tambora Peninsula and Moyo Island, and connected to the Flores Sea by a narrow strait. The bay supports diverse habitats including coral reefs, mangroves, and seagrass beds, and benefits from nutrient input via riverine discharge and seasonal upwelling, making it a highly productive marine environment. The bay is recognised as an important aggregation site for whale sharks (*Rhincodon typus*), hosting one of the largest known populations in Indonesia. Most individuals are juvenile males, with many showing strong site fidelity — some returning repeatedly over several years. Feeding opportunities are abundant due to high plankton density and the presence of small shrimp, particularly in areas influenced by mangroves. A unique behavioural interaction also occurs between whale sharks and traditional fishing platforms (bagans), where sharks are often observed feeding at the surface near these structures. In 2024, Saleh Bay was officially recognised by the IUCN as a key site for whale shark foraging and migration. Conservation initiatives are ongoing, including the development of a marine protected area and the establishment of a whale shark education centre in Labuan Jambu. Despite its ecological importance, the area faces challenges such as destructive fishing practices and habitat degradation. Continued protection and sustainable management are essential to safeguarding this critical habitat.

Figure 38: Geographical location of Saleh Bay, Sumbawa, Indonesia, Indian Ocean.

- **Period of occurrence**

IMAR team (Figure 39) participated in an international mission from 14th to 25th June 2025 partially supported also by Konservasi Indonesia and Elasmobranch Institute Indonesia, who invited the IMAR team to collaborate with their study on the ecology of the whale shark and demonstrate this European technology developed by the NAUTILOS project to researchers from Asia. Successful deployments were achieved with whale sharks (Figure 40). All tags deployed were recovered and once, MAANTA NAUTILOS tag was found floating, after pop-up from a whale shark, by a diving operator boat and returned to the IMAR team by tourists (Figure 41).

Figure 39: IMAR and Konservasi Indonesia/Elasmobranch Institute Indonesia teams showing a recovered MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag in Saleh Bay, Sumbawa, Indonesia.

Figure 40: Whale shark tagged with MAANTA NAUTILOS in Saleh Bay, Indonesia.

Figure 41: MAANTA NAUTILOS tag found floating after pop-up from a whale shark by a diving operator boat and returned to the IMAR team by tourists.

- **Data recovery**

The data from all deployments (Table 1) was successfully retrieved from the LITE units. As for the Atlantic and Pacific Oceans, all the retrieved raw data was uploaded in the NAUTILOS cloud drive (Figure 11). After data quality check, the operational data was uploaded by IMAR to the NAUTILOS FTP server (Figure 12) and, thus, included in the NAUTILOS ERDDAP™ repository (according to the project data sharing scheme made by ETT - Deliverables 8.3 and 8.4).

The oxygen profile from a whale shark track reveals a clear stratification of dissolved oxygen (DO) along the vertical axis (Figure 42). High concentrations of DO ($>200 \mu\text{mol/L}$) are observed in surface waters (0–20 m), followed by a pronounced decline with increasing depth. Between approximately 50 m and 150 m, oxygen levels drop significantly, reaching values below $100 \mu\text{mol/L}$, indicating a midwater oxygen minimum zone. At depths greater than 150 m, oxygen concentrations appear to stabilise or slightly recover. This vertical pattern is consistent with the influence of tropical water column structure and restricted circulation in semi-enclosed bays such as Saleh Bay. All values fall within the expected environmental range for dissolved oxygen in this region.

Figure 42: Depth (left) and vertical oxygen (right) profiles from a whale shark (*Rhincodon typus*) track (WS-05) in Saleh Bay, Indonesia. Dissolved oxygen concentrations ($\mu\text{mol/L}$) recorded by the MAANTA NAUTILOS tag are plotted against depth. The data illustrate a typical stratified profile, with high surface oxygen levels and a marked decline through the midwater column.

- **Maintenance, events/issues occurred and actions taken**

No issues to report.

6. RESULTS - COMMENTS - CONCLUSIONS

- **Results**

As described in this chapter, during WP7 activities all targeted species were successfully tagged, along with two additional charismatic species - whale sharks and shortfin mako sharks - tagged opportunistically. In addition to expanding the species range, IMAR actively participated in international expeditions to broaden the geographical scope of the demonstration. One such expedition took place in early 2025 in the Pacific Ocean (Colombia), aiming to tag ragged tooth sand tiger sharks. Another, in June 2025 in the Indian Ocean (Indonesia), focused on the tagging of juvenile whale sharks. These efforts contributed to enhance the demonstrability of the task and to the global expansion of the MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag demonstrations (Figure 43).

Figure 43: AXE: MAANTA NAUTILOS deployments across the three different oceans: Atlantic, Pacific and Indian.

By the end of the NAUTILOS project, the MAANTA NAUTILOS tags had achieved a total of 35 deployments across the Atlantic, Pacific, and Indian Oceans, including 23 deployments on animals (Table 5), accounting for almost 500 hours of data and around 1600 hours on water. Since the deployment season commenced in 2024, these units have remained watertight even at depths exceeding 1200 m, thereby demonstrating the success of the structural improvements. Throughout this period of intensive activity, tags were deployed and recovered within short weather windows, thereby maximising reuse and efficiency. Notably, 100% of the deployed tags on animals (n = 23) were successfully recovered, even when some units surfaced as far as approximately 135 nautical miles from Faial Island, demonstrating the effectiveness of the deployment and recovery protocols. The mission duration for these specific activities was planned for 24 to 48 hours (to avoid tagging animals on migration; priority was given to the continuous data acquisition mode), however the actual deployment duration (i.e., time the equipment remained in the water) varied significantly, from 0.10 hours to 286 hours.

Table 5: MAANTA NAUTILOS deployments on animals and test drops deployments at sea.

SPECIES	NUMBER OF DEPLOYMENTS
Bluntnose sixgill shark (<i>H. griseus</i>)	3 (Atlantic Ocean)
Shortfin mako shark (<i>I. oxyrinchus</i>)	1 (Atlantic Ocean)
Blue shark (<i>P. glauca</i>)	7 (Atlantic Ocean)
Chilean devil ray (<i>M. tarapacana</i>)	4 (Atlantic Ocean)
Whale shark (<i>R. typus</i>)	4 (Atlantic Ocean)
Human deployment (H.sapiens)	1 (Pacific Ocean)
Whale shark (<i>R. typus</i>)	4 (Indian Ocean)
Total deployments on animals	23
Test drops deployments (Matosinhos & Azores)	2 Matosinhos + 9 Azores
Total deployments	24+11 =35

Considering the major challenges faced with the mechanical integration and unclear calibration information, those results demonstrate the CEiiA and IMAR team’s ability to overcome unexpected challenges through intensive problem-solving and additional effort. However, this troubleshooting process’s complexity and time delayed animal-borne deployments, reduced the expected time available for deployments however without consequences as several good data was acquired and made available, following NAUTILOS data sharing protocols. Also, these activities significantly improved the reliability of the DO measurements and restored confidence in the sensor performance, in time for both international missions. These improvements supported the continued evolution of the MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag during WP7, towards full commercialisation, which is expected in the near future.

The final mission in Indonesia was reported with no issues. As previously mentioned, shared datasets provided oxygen profiles revealing a clear stratification of dissolved oxygen (DO) with depth (Figure 42). This vertical pattern (high concentrations of DO in surface waters, followed by a pronounced decline with increasing depth, stabilisation/ slightly recover at depths greater than 150 m) is consistent with the influence of tropical water column structure and restricted circulation in semi-enclosed bays such as Saleh Bay. All values fall within the expected environmental range for dissolved oxygen in this region.

- **TRL achievement level and project SOP**

Due to all reported work and improvements, MAANTA NAUTILOS Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) declared is TRL8.

- **Future plans and Recommendations**

Both MAANTA NAUTILOS units will remain available for future deployments with IMAR Team, as the manufacturer (CEiiA) intends to continue monitoring the equipment while it is still in the prototype phase to understand the state of corrosion and deterioration and monitor the quality of the data acquired with time.

There are some improvements identified for the near future that need to be evaluated (as they differ significantly in complexity) between both teams and depending on time-budget availability. From expected easier developments such as to adapt the used-defined dissolved oxygen sampling rate, to deep mechanical modifications such as to replace final solution developed for WP7 for a solution for 2000m deep (like the other items in the MAANTA NAUTILOS tags as containers, lids and sensors; and MAANTA product line in general).

1. BACKGROUND

As the Oxygen Minimum Zone is expanding, animal-borne oxygen tags can provide extremely valuable information especially in the context of poorly sampled areas such as the Southern Ocean (SO). The development of original conductivity-temperature-depth satellite relayed data logger (CTD-SRDL) tags deployed on southern elephant seals since 2003/2004, led to a significant increase in samples of vertical oceanographic profiles in the remote Southern Ocean. Southern elephant seals contribute to the collection of 80 % of the temperature and salinity profiles south of 60°S and 98% of the profiles associated with the Antarctic sea-ice. This methodology was very efficient at delivering near-real-time physical oceanographic data as well as new behavioural information on free-ranging seals, which explore large areas in the SO. As part of NAUTILOS we included a new oxygen sensor into the existing CTD-SRDL tag to sample this critical biogeochemical parameter in the South Atlantic and the SO relying on Southern elephant seals.

2. DEMONSTRATION PLAN ON SOUTHERN OCEAN WITH ELEPHANT SEALS

- **Specific Objectives**

In the scope of T7.5 from NAUTILOS project, CNRS tested a new stage of development of the animal-borne instruments with the addition of a sensor measuring dissolved oxygen in the Argos CTD-SRDL tags from the Sea Mammal Research Unit - the SRDL-CTD-Oxy. Measurements obtained from these new devices deployed on elephant seals, in the oceanographic and biogeochemical context of the Southern Ocean (SO), are present in the present in D7.6. The quality and accuracy of the measurements was investigated using the climatology of oxygen concentration from World Ocean Atlas, GLORYS ocean model and Argo floats equipped with an oxygen sensor. Demonstration activities, conducted in the Peninsula Valdes (PV) and Kerguelen Island (KI), show how monitoring this parameter on the long-term using top predators improves the observational database of dissolved oxygen in the SO and represents a new opportunity to investigate the relationship between air-breathing marine predators and the other components of marine ecosystems.

In addition to the (SRDL-CTD-Oxy) an active and miniaturized sonar tag integrating a high sensitivity high-frequency light sensor to assess bioluminescence was deployed. Zooplankton and micronekton are the crucial link between phytoplankton and upper predators, and as such, they are referred to as the Mid Trophic Levels (MTL). MTL inhabiting the mesopelagic biome (0-1000 m, represent by far the most abundant animal biota on Earth. SO mesopelagic MTL encompass a large diversity of zooplankton: crustaceans (amphipods, copepods, euphausiids...) and non-crustacean species such as gelatinous tunicates (i.e. salps) and micronekton consisting of small (~2-20 cm) mesopelagic fish (dominated, in the SO, by bioluminescent lantern fish or myctophids), cephalopods (squids) and hydrozoans (i.e. jellyfish). Mesopelagic MTL generates conspicuous sound-scattering layers readily captured by echo-sounders during their diel vertical migration; this behaviour contributes efficiently to carbon export to the deep ocean.

- **Platform/equipment involved**

The tagging systems aimed at adding an oxygen sensor to the already existing Temperature, Salinity and Pressure Satellite Data Relayed logger (SRDL-CTD-Oxy) to track large, deep diving (up to 2000 m) air breathing marine animals (seals and turtles) while recording their behavioral (diving and activity) and

sampling oceanographic conditions (T, S, Oxy, Pressure) during the dive. This device (SRDL-CTD-Oxy) was conceived to provide oceanographic quality Temperature (0.01°C effective accuracy), Salinity (0.03 PSU effective accuracy), Oxygen (1 $\mu\text{mol.l}^{-1}$ accuracy) and pressure (2 dBar accuracy).

As part of the NAUTILOS project, a small size and low cost oxygen sensor oxygen FD-OEM-O2 Optical Oxygen Sensor (Table 6) developed by Pyroscience (Germany) was decided to be the best choice. It was incorporated into the existing CTD SRDL developed by the Sea Mammal Research Unit (University of Saint Andrews, United Kingdom), with CEBC-CNRS (France) collaboration.

Table 6: Main features of FD-OEM-O2 from Pyroscience.

FD-OEM-O2 main features				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-accuracy measurement in gas or in water (DO) • Low drift • Long lifetime • Fast response • Digital output of all major oxygen units • Temperature compensation • Low power consumption • Small dimensions • Lead free 				
Specific mechanical features				
Dimensions		Ø 26,3 mm x 19 mm		
Weight		5 g		
Distance Optics – Sensor Spot		max. 20 mm, may be extended with light guide		
Conformity to RoHS directive		RoHS compliant, lead free		
Analytical Performance (with OXSP5 Sensor Spot)				
Oxygen unit	hPa	%O2*	% air sat.*	mg/L
Medium	gas/water	gas	water	water
Typ. measuring range	0-500	0-50	0-250	0-23
Max. measuring range	0-2000	0-200	0-500	0-50
Detection limit	0.1	0.01	0.05	0.005
Resolution at 10 hPa	0.1	0.01	0.05	0.005
Resolution at 200 hPa	0.5	0.05	0.25	0.025
Accuracy at 10 hPa (10°C – 40°C)	±0.2	±0.02	±0.1	±0.01

Accuracy at 200 hPa (10°C – 40°C)	±2	±0.2	±1	±0.1
Accuracy at 10 hPa (-10°C – 60°C)	±1	±0.1	±0.5	±0.05
Accuracy at 200 hPa (-10°C – 60°C)	±10	±1	±5	±0.5
Response time (t90)	< 15 sec (water), <5 sec (gas)**			
Drift @ 25°C	<1% O2 / year at 20% O2			
Minimum lifetime	>50,000,000 measurements			
Storage life	>5 years in darkness at 20°C			
Warm-up time	3 min (reduced accuracy during warm-up)			
* at 1013 mbar ambient gas pressure ** faster response times on request				

The FD-OEM-O2 is an optical oxygen sensor module for OEM (original equipment manufacturer) applications based on luminescence quenching of a sensor dye that is immobilized on a support foil (“sensor spot”). It can be used for gas measurements as well as for dissolved oxygen (DO) on liquids. The sensor spot is excited with red light, and the properties of the emitted luminescence are measured in the near infrared. The presence of molecular oxygen quenches the luminescence, changing its intensity and lifetime fully reversibly (Figure 44). A distance between the opto-electronics and the sensor spot of up to 20 mm is possible. This gap can be filled with air or any transparent material that has no fluorescence in the NIR (glass, polycarbonate, PMMA, PET, etc.). The measurement principle is very robust. It shows virtually no interference to other gases and laboratory experiments showed a very low drift over time, and the sensor is fully solid-state.

Figure 44: Principle of the Oxygen measurement implemented in the FD-OEM-O2.

Oxygen sensors were fitted on the CTD SRDL (Figure 45). The electronic part was integrated into the CTD SRDL with the oxygen sensor protruding on the side of the SRDL (picture). The overall size, weight and volume of the SRDL-CTD-Oxy tag were 10 x 7 x 4 cm and 535g in air (about 200 g in water) and ~250 cm³. This represents less than 0.15 % of the mass of an average adult female southern elephant seal (~350 kg). The SRDL-CTD-Oxy tag was designed to sustain a maximum of 200 bars and to sample and transmit near real time up to four temperature/salinity/oxygen (T/S/O) profiles per day.

The FD-OEM-O2 features built-in temperature compensation and a digital interface that provides oxygen measurements in engineering units. However, due to the low resolution and extended response time of the integrated temperature FD-OEM-O2 sensor it had to be adapted for our application, in particular for two reasons:

- First due to the high vertical speed of seals (about 1.5 m.s⁻¹) the fast response version had to be implemented to reduce the vertical lag in O measurements;
- Second, originally this sensor was designed to sustain 20 bar (~200 m). As the seals are diving on

average at 400-500 m but up to 2000 m the sensor had to be modified to sustain such pressure. To do so the electronic part was fully cast in the epoxy, with the exception of the membrane which had to be directly exposed to the water. fully cast in epoxy when integrated into the CTD-SRDL.

Figure 45: Integration of the Pyroscience FD-OEM-O2, oxygen sensor on the side of the SMRU SRDL-CTD-Oxy (left) and a female elephant seal equipped with a SRDL-CTD-Oxy tag in PV, Argentina 2021.

While temperature and salinity data are sampled and archived continuously at 0.5 Hz through the whole deployment, oxygen measurements, due to high-energy consumption, are only sampled during the ascent phase of four selected dives each day. The near real time transmitted T/S/O profiles are selected during the quasi-vertical ascent of seals [Roquet et al., 2011], retaining only the deepest dive in each 6 h time interval. Each profile is reduced to 24 data points of T/S and O using a broken stick algorithm applied on T data to minimize the difference between the High Resolution (HR) and Low Resolution (LR) profiles with selected salinity and oxygen matching those the retained temperature data points. The 24 T/S and O LR profiles are then transmitted profiles form through the Advanced Research and Global Observation Satellite (ARGOS) system. Animal positions are determined using ARGOS telemetry information, with a typical accuracy of ± 5 km. High Resolution T/S and Oxygen data can be recovered if the tag is recovered when the seal is back on land after its at-sea foraging trip.

The tags were tested and pre-calibrated in an experimental set up conducted by SMRU (Scotland, UK; Appendix 6).

In addition to SRDL-CTD-Oxy tag, high frequency (1.5 MHz) sonar tags, i.e. miniature echosounder (micro-sonar) integrating a high sensitivity high-frequency light sensor to assess bioluminescence was deployed on elephant seals to assess its potential value in evaluating the poorly known but critical mid-trophic level organisms.

- **Locations, period and deployment method**

As part of NAUTILOS, the initial plan was to deploy 10 CTD-Oxy SRDL on post-breeding southern elephant seal females in Valdes Peninsula (PV), Argentina. However, due to the avian flu epidemic the deployment strongly affected the PV elephant seal population, with a female mortality of about 50% and a pup mortality of 97% (Campagna et al. 2025]). Therefore, the 2023 and 2024 deployments were not possible in (2023) and not authorized (2024) in PV by Argentinian authorities and consequently were relocated at Kerguelen Island (KI) to finalize NAUTILOS demonstration activities. Three demonstration study sites were considered in the scope of NAUTILOS (Figure 46). The last deployment occurred in Kerguelen Island, starting in October 2024, thus concluding the 10 expected deployments in the scope of NAUTILOS project (Table 7).

Figure 46: Three demonstration study sites were considered in the scope of Nautilus, where female southern elephant seals were equipped with the SRDL-CTD-Oxy tag: one at Peninsula Valdes (PV) and two at Kerguelen Island (KI).

Table 7: Southern Ocean deployments performed over 3 seasons: 2021; 2023 and 2024.

TAG NUMBER	DEPLOYMENT LOCATION	AT SEA DEPARTURE	RETURN TO SHORE	TAG RECOVERED	DATA	REMARKS
15555	PV	23/10/21	5/01/22	yes	Partly	Issues with the on-board processing of the oxygen data up to 300 m
15556	PV	20/10/21	19/12/21	yes	Ok	Tag stop transmitting oxygen profiles on the 29/11/21 (224 CTD-Oxy profiles)
15557	PV	20/10/21	25/12/21	yes	Ok	302 CTD-Oxy profiles
15558	PV	20/10/21	18/12/21	yes	No	No oxygen data transmitted
15559	PV	20/10/21	27/12/21	yes	Ok	96 CTD-Oxy profiles
15828	KI	11/10/23	20/12/23	Yes	No	No oxygen data transmitted
15829	KI	19/10/23	19/12/23	yes	No	No oxygen data transmitted
15557	KI	8/10/23	21/12/23	No	Partly	7 profiles transmitted at the beginning of the deployment
15828	KI	7/10/24	11/12/24	Yes	Partly	10 Oxygen profiles at the beginning of the foraging trip
15829	KI	8/10/24	24/10/24	Yes	Ok	347 CTD-Oxy profiles transmitted. 347 HR CTD-Oxy profiles recovered

Females were equipped with the CTD-Oxy SRDL tag and a small Argos only tag (Spot 5, Wildlife Computer (70 X 41 X 23 mm, 72 g) to facilitate the recovery of the SRDL-CTD-Oxy in case it has stopped transmitting prior to the return to shore. Post-breeding females leave shore ~ between the 10th-30th of October for a

foraging trip lasting 70 to 90 days and covering 4000 ± 450 km before they return to shore in summer to molt allowing the recovery of the tags and the archived data. In addition to tag deployments (Table 7), four southern elephant seal females were equipped with a micro-sonar provided by SMRU.

Handling elephant seals requires their immobilization using anesthetic drugs. The procedure consists in injecting an intramuscular dose of Zoletil 100, a 1:1 mixture of tiletamine and zolazepam using a 10 cm long needle - connected to a syringe by a 250 cm long 2 mm in diameter tubulure containing the zoletil and the syringe filled with physiological serum. Resting seals were approached on foot (Figure 47). The dose injected was approximately 0.8 mL per 100 kg of estimated live weight. As reported in the ethics section (see below) the anesthetic procedure follows the legal framework. The tags were attached with cable ties on a net-mesh base. This base (with the tag) was glued to elephant seals fur using double component fast setting epoxy. At tag recovery, cable ties are cut and the tag collected. The base was left glued onto the fur. It detaches itself during the elephant seal moult. Elephant seals undertake what is called a catastrophic moult. During that process they lose all their hair as well as the upper part of the epidermis. Therefore, nothing remains on the seals after the moult.

Figure 47: Anesthesia of a male elephant seal for the recovery of the bilogger when returning to shore (KI).

- **Data recovery**

SRDL-CTD-Oxy data recovery

Out of the 10 tags deployed, 9 were recovered. During the demonstrations (Table 7), a total of 979 validated CTD-oxy profiles were transmitted near real time through the Argos system. In addition the latest tag deployed at KI (15828 and 15829) was able to collect HR CTD-Oxy profiles up to 4 times per day (Figure 48).

Figure 48: Argos tracks of the 10 southern elephant seal females equipped with a SRDL-CTD-Oxy, in PV (2021, n=5, left) in and at KI (2023, n=3 and 2024, n=2, right).

The data were sent to ETT by uploading it in TXT format via FTP to the NAUTILOS server. The files were then gathered into a single dataset on the NAUTILOS ERDDAP™ managed by ETT: https://data-nautilus-h2020.eu/erddap/tabledap/elephant_seals_cnrs.html. The dataset is then made available by CNR-ISTI to NAUTILOS Data Portal (Figure 49).

Figure 49: NAUTILOS data portal displaying Elephant Seals data.

Micro-sonar data recovery

As part of NAUTILOS, 4 micro-sonars were deployed on SES in total:

- 2 deployed in PV in 2022 and 2 at Kerguelen Island in 2022;
- 3 recovered: 2 in PV and 1 at KI.

Micro-sonar recorded acoustic backscatter data while the seals foraged respectively in the Indian and the Atlantic sectors of the Southern Ocean. The micro-sonar data was fully recovered for those 3 recaptured seals, providing a unique set of new data to assess the Mid Trophic Level organisms.

- **Maintenance, events/issues occurred and actions taken**

The recovery of 9 out of the 10 SRDL-CTD-Oxy tags deployed allowed an in-depth analysis of the possible causes of tag failures. These causes were of two different nature of completely different origins:

- 1) The degradation/ loss of the oxygen measuring membrane. This issue is not yet fully resolved as one of the two tags deployed at KI in 2024 was exposed to that issue. In a way to try reducing it, a protection cap was added to reduce direct exposure to the light and direct contact with sand which may damage the membrane which proved to work during 2024 deployment
- 2) In 2023, the failure was unrelated to the oxygen measurement but related to a general issue with the CTD sensor produced by Valeport who modified, without informing its customers the design of the CTD sensor in a way to simplify its production and reduce the production cost. This change resulted in a progressive ingress of salt water in relation to variation of pressure the CTD sensor was exposed in successive dives, which remained undetected in the lab test. The ingress of salt water resulted in the progressive loss of part or all the tag function. Thanks to the recovery of the tags that allowed us to identify the problem, this issue has now been resolved.

All data transmitted is stored on board, at HR, for temperature and salinity. On the most recent generation of tags deployed in 2023 and 2024, also HR oxygen data was stored onboard.

- **Data analysis and quality assess**

Data stored onboard the tags are being extracted after deployments. Methods vary for SRDL-CTD-Oxy tags and micro-sonar and will be detailed below.

SRDL-CTD-Oxy data analysis

Data stored onboard the tags was extracted and checked for validation/correction prior to their distribution to the community via the MEOP/ANIBOS Portal according to (Roquet et al. 2011; Roquet et al. 2014). Once a deployment was completed (i.e. the tag was recovered) recovered profiles went through a series of tests to assess their quality :

- comparison with the local climatological temperature/salinity/oxygen profiles;
- detection of anomalous spikes;
- inter-comparison with in-situ profiles provided by Argo floats and/or oceanographic vessels which were co-localized in time and space.

An example of the Temperature, Salinity and Oxygen profiles transmitted through the Argos system is presented for one seal equipped at KI in 2024 in Figure 50 and Figure 51.

Figure 50: Track of the seal equipped with the SRDL-CTD-Oxy 15829 at Kerguelen Island and the total record of Temperature, salinity and oxygen profiles performed between the 8/10 and 24/12/2024.

Figure 51: High Resolution Oxygen profiles (n=347) recovered from the tag 15829 de played act KI in October 2024. Oxygen measurements due to high-energy requirements were only sampled 4 times per day at 0.5 Hz, while Temperature and Salinity were continuously sampled at 0.5 Hz through the complete foraging trip.

The temperature salinity profiles were corrected according to the procedure described in Roquet et al. (2014) while an oxygen data quality assessment had to be developed. As part of Nautilus oxygen quality assessment was performed according to i) climatological data available for the corresponding area, ii) oxygen ocean model data and iii) concomitant Argo float oxygen data.

One of the main difficulties was to properly assess the data quality once the tags were deployed on seal. This was achieved by three different methods:

- 1) Comparison with the world oceanographic atlas providing Oxygen climatological value at a 1° spatial resolution at different depth (<https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/products/world-ocean-atlas>; Reagan et al. 2024);
- 2) With the Glorys model, provided by Copernicus Marine System;
- 3) With Argo oxygen data co-localized in time and space with the southern elephant seal data.

An example for each method is presented below.

1. Comparison with the World Atlas Oxygen data.

The in-situ oxygen profiles collected by the CTD-Oxy SRDL are within the range of World Ocean Atlas both for PV and KI.

Surface and 250 m oxygen values provided by the SRDL are within the range of the World Ocean Atlas oxygen value for the corresponding region (surface 320-340 $\mu\text{mol.l}^{-1}$; 300 m: 210-255 $\mu\text{mol.l}^{-1}$). It is unclear if the seasonal change we observed is related to a sensor drift over-time or is real. Literature reviews for the Southern Ocean reveal significant seasonal variations are observed in the amount of dissolved oxygen at surface with oxygen values being higher by $6.8 \pm 1.2 \mu\text{mol.l}^{-1}$ in summer compared to spring (Bushinsky et al. 2017). Seal in-situ data suggest a 8 $\mu\text{mol.l}^{-1}$ oxygen enrichment in summer compared to spring (Bushinsky et al. 2017). The larger variation observed at 300 m might be related to the seasonal change in Mixed Layer Properties, with the mixed layer shallowing by nearly 80 m between mid-October and mid-December (Figure 52).

Figure 52: Comparison of the Oxygen profiles sampled by an elephant seal close to KI for the outward and inward trip (two month apart) of the seal equipped with the SRDL 15829. Seal data suggest an increase in oxygen values at the surface between spring and summer in the area in the red frame (to the bottom left).

2. Comparison with the Glorys Model data

The in-situ seal oxygen profiles values match well the colocalized in space and time oxygen profiles extracted from Glorys model (Figure 53). However, and as expected the in-situ seal data exhibit a much greater vertical and horizontal variability compared to the model.

Figure 53: Comparison of the seal sampled oxygen (in red) at PV with the oxygen profiles from Glorys co-localized (in green) in time (day) and space (0.1°).

3. Comparison to the in-situ Oxygen Argo data.

Seal in-situ CTD-Oxy profiles were compared with in-situ profiles provided within the PV or KI area. However, this comparison is not possible on profile-to-profile basis due to the near impossibility of sampling simultaneously an oxygen profile with a seal equipped with a CTD-Oxy SRDL and an Argo Float with an oxygen sensor. However as shown in Figure 54 the Seal oxygen profiles sampled in PV are within the envelope of the Argo float profiles. The same is observed at KI.

Figure 54: Comparison of the seal sampled oxygen in PV (in red) with the oxygen profiles from Glorys co-localized (in green) in time (day) and space (0.1°).

Micro-sonar data analysis

The micro-sonar allows us to estimate time series of scatterer density versus depth, expressed in scatterers m³, their apparent size, their acoustic intensity and over time their behavior (i.e. if they perform or not diel vertical migration (Figure 55 and Figure 56).

Figure 55: Time series of scatterer density versus depth, expressed in scatterers m³, for ml19_295a, a female SES equipped with sonar and oceanographic tags in the Kerguelen Islands in 2019 during its post-breeding foraging trip. Coloured rectangles above the plot indicate day (yellow) and night (purple) cycle, and the associated Functional Oceanographic Domain assessed from the in-situ temperature and salinity profiles.

The backscatter varied widely over time and space, and the seals attempted to capture only a small fraction of the insonified targets. Diel vertical migration patterns were clearly identifiable in the data, reinforcing our confidence in the ability of the sonar tags to detect living mid-trophic organisms along with possibly sinking biological detritus. Moreover, CTD tags attached to the same animals indicated how the abundance, size distribution, and diel migration behaviour of acoustic targets varied with water bodies. These preliminary results demonstrate the potential of the micro-sonar to provide detailed in-situ information on the MTL.

Despite the sonar tag's minimal resolution being approximately 3.9 mm, objects of 1 mm size can be detected, even though organisms from 1 to 3.9 mm are included in the same apparent acoustic size class. This sensitivity suggests that the sonar tag can detect small organisms such as mesoplankton and micronekton (secondary consumers, between 2 and 20 cm). Copepods, the predominant components of zooplankton, could contribute to the acoustic signal received. Euphausiids, commonly encountered within regions, are also likely to contribute to these signals. However, the biological nature of these acoustically detected scatterers remains unconfirmed at this stage.

Figure 56: Functional Oceanographic Domain (right) for the Kerguelen region in November 2022 and left the Size abundance spectra of particles assessed by the micro-sonar for each Functional Oceanographic Domain. (Log scale). The constant value at the origin provides information about differences in abundance of particles between Functional Oceanographic Domain, while the slope of the spectra is an indicator of the energy transfer efficiency between size classes, the steeper the less efficient this energy transfer is.

3. RESULTS - COMMENTS - CONCLUSIONS

- **Results**

Out of the 10 tags deployed, 9 were recovered. During the demonstrations (Table 7), a total of 979 validated CTD-oxy profiles were transmitted near real time through the Argos system. In addition, the latest tag deployed at KI was able to collect HR CTD-Oxy profiles up to 4 times per day.

The CTD-Oxy SRDL provided valuable oxygen results:

- results are in line with the World Ocean Atlas oxygen data as well as the in-situ oxygen profiles range provided by Argo floats;
- accuracy range is estimated to be about 2-5 $\mu\text{mol.l}^{-1}$ in a well pre-deployment calibrated CTD-Oxy SRDL.

Not all the 10 CTD-Oxy SRDL deployed worked properly as there was a reliability issue of the CTD-Oxy SRDL. Thanks to the field demonstration activities, the causes have been identified and are being solved, allowing the commercialisation of CTD-Oxy SRDL by the Sea Mammal Research Unit in the near future.

In addition to sampling the oceanographic conditions of the water column, the data collected represent a major contribution to the investigation of the at-sea foraging ecology of studied species in relation to the encountered oceanographic conditions. As such, they play a key role in marine conservation by helping research scientists relate an animal's behavior to its surrounding environment.

As it concerns the micro-sonar, the data collected on the Mid Trophic levels are of considerable interest. The micro-sonar data provides information on the variation in the biological richness and composition and how they vary according to the oceanographic context visited by the SES. The result obtained from the elephant seal demonstration emphasizes the value of integrating this device into an Argo Float.

- **TRL achievement level and project SOP**

Due to all reported work and improvements, Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) declared is TRL8.

- **Future plans and Recommendations**

Future plans and recommendations for the CTD-Oxy SRDL include the need for some testing, to keep improving the instrument capability and to start commercialisation.

According to the work performed, there is a need to increase the reliability of the oxygen measurement of the CTD-Oxy SRDL tag. The issues have been identified and already partly solved. Further work should be performed to secure the fixation and protection from possible physical contact and direct exposure to sunlight of the oxygen measurement membrane. A protection cap has been designed and will be incorporated in the next generation of the oxygen tag to be tested, however other ideas will also be explored if necessary along the way. Also, although the overall quality of the oxygen measurements provided by the oxygen tags match well the existing in-situ oxygen data sets as well as the known seasonal variations, more at sea testing along a CTD Oxygen rosette are needed to evaluate precisely the accuracy and the time response of the oxygen sensor.

CTD-Oxy SRDL tags are not yet advertised for sale on the web site, but can be bought to SMRU by regular customers, with a replacement option of the oxygen sensor in case the oxygen measurements fail. An upgraded and reliable version should be available for sale in the course of 2026.

IV. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

1. DATA PROTECTION

The integration of multiple sensors in the tag system introduces ethical considerations related to data protection. While increased data collection improves understanding of animal behavior and habitats, it is crucial to ensure the integrity and security of the data collected. Notably, the system does not record or store personal data and therefore falls outside the scope of EU data protection legislation.

Under Task 7.5, raw and processed data are exchanged exclusively among project partners for joint analysis and to support the system's TRL advancement during demonstration phases. No interaction with external stakeholders is foreseen within the MAANTA demonstration activities in WP7. Information shared publicly is limited to dissemination purposes and adheres to project communication guidelines.

Additionally, all oceanographic data (T/S/oxy) collected with SRDL-CTD-Oxy, as part of NAUTILOS, are contributing to the observation of the global Ocean and are made available through the MEOP portal and through the ANIBOS network of Global Ocean Observing System once they have been post-calibrated, validated.

2. ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION

Batteries

Both NAUTILOS animal tags have an internal rechargeable battery, and in the case of losing the equipment (if recovery is not possible) there would be no danger for the environment.

For the MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag, it is installed in a metallic container, and the equipment will always be on the surface as long as it has a positive buoyancy. Furthermore, according to the battery specifications, battery cells do not contain any environmentally hazardous components such as lead or cadmium. Cells should be discarded in a discharged state to avoid heat generation from inadvertent short circuits.

The CTD-Oxy SRDL has an internal battery, and in the case of losing the equipment (if recovery is not possible) there would be no danger for the environment as it is fully cast into the epoxy if lost ashore and not recovered. If recovered the batteries are sent to the proper recycling facility when the tag is refurbished. If the tag is lost at sea it will implode due to high pressure (>200 bars) but according to the battery specifications, the battery cells do not contain any environmentally hazardous components such as lead or cadmium.

WEEE considerations

The disposal of both NAUTILOS animal tags follow the Directive 2012/19/EU on Waste from Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE). Electronics have a long-life expectancy as both systems have a high recovery rate (between 90 and 100%).

In accordance with local laws and regulations, the equipment and/or its battery must be disposed of in a dedicated battery container. When this device reaches the end of its life, take it to a collection point designated by the local authorities. The separate collection and recycling of the device and/or its battery at the time of disposal will help conserve natural resources and ensure that it is recycled in a way that protects human health and the environment.

Batteries

MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag is composed of a rechargeable battery (INR18350) and a non-rechargeable lithium button cell battery (CR927) to power the system's internal clock. As mentioned in the Deliverable 5.8 cells are deployed inside a metallic container to resist high pressures. Besides all the electronics designed to avoid any malfunction of the batteries, in case of any problem occurring with the cells (*e.g.* explosion), the container prevents any possible leak to the environment. Batteries must be handled with care and must not be in contact with water/sea water.

The CTD-Oxy SRDL tag is composed of a non-rechargeable lithium D-cell size (Saft LSH20 D 13000mAh 3.6V 4A Lithium-Thionyl Chloride) battery. Replacement of the battery is performed at SMRU under laboratory fume hood and batteries must be handled with care and must not be in contact with water/sea water during that process.

Dangerous goods

As mentioned above, both NAUTILOS animal tags have batteries that are classified as Class 9 of the UN model regulation (Recommendations on the Transport of Dangerous Goods).

For MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tags, since the cells can be transported outside the electronics, the shipping type regulation is different from that shown in Deliverable 5.8 (Chapter II, section 3 - Health and Safety). Each battery has transport safety certified according to transport regulation UN38.3, which means it has passed the environmental, electrical and mechanical safety requirements. The battery transport certificate (UN38.8) of each battery must always be submitted to the logistics company before transportation.

CTD-Oxy SRDL animal tags have transport safety certified according to transport regulation UN 3481 (lithium battery within an equipment). Each CTD-Oxy SRDL tag must always be submitted to the logistics company before transportation.

4. PROTECTION OF MARINE LIFE

As mentioned in chapter II, section 4 of deliverable 5.8, despite biologging technologies have produced new insights into the ecology and behaviour of marine animals, most studies still involve invasive methods for capturing and restraining animals for tag deployment. This way, animal welfare is the central factor for any biologist, scientist and engineers responsible for the development of technology, as it happened with both NAUTILOS animal tags. Depending on study location and species involved, it is critical to take into consideration the impact of the tag system on the animal behaviour, health or welfare of the animal.

In particular, the main goal of the MAANTA NAUTILOS system is to be deployed in a way to avoid any harm to marine life. The MAANTA NAUTILOS is non-invasive since it is towed by the animal, causing no harm to the animals and when it is released it is collected from the water.

Also, the main goal of the CTD-Oxy SRDL tag is to be deployed in a way to avoid any harm to marine life. The tags were glued to their fur using a fast-setting, low-exothermic araldite resin. They were recovered using the same anaesthetic procedure in December or January, when the females returned to land to moult. This project was approved by ComEth Anses/ENVA/UPEC (permit N° 19-040 21375) and positively evaluated by the TAAF Polar Environment Committee.

The CTD-Oxy SRDL is minimally invasive since it is glued to the air of the animal using towed by the animal, causing no harm to the animals.

It is important to highlight that major considerations are described in D13.3 that outlines the general information on the nature of the experiments, and the procedures to ensure animal welfare and adherence to EU Directive 2010/63/EU “on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes” and to the Three Rs principle.

5. DUAL USE POTENTIAL

No dual use potential has been identified for NAUTILUS animal tags.

APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

ID	Reference or Related Document	Source or Link/Location
1	Pico-O2-SUB - OEM Fiber-Optic Oxygen Meter - Manual	https://www.pyroscience.com/en/products/all-meters/pico-o2-sub#downloads
2	Reagan, James R.; Boyer, Tim P.; García, Hernán E.; Locarnini, Ricardo A.; Baranova, Olga K.; Bouchard, Courtney; Cross, Scott L.; Mishonov, Alexey V.; Paver, Christopher R.; Seidov, Dan; Wang, Zhankun; Dukhovskoy, Dmitry. (2024). World Ocean Atlas 2023. NOAA National Centers for Environmental Information.	https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/metadata/landing-page/bin/iso?id=gov.noaa.nodc:0270533
	Bushinsky SM, Gray AR, Johnson KS, Sarmiento JL (2017). Oxygen in the Southern Ocean From Argo Floats: Determination of Processes Driving Air-Sea Fluxes. J. Geoph. Res =, 122, 8661-8682.	doi.org/10.1002/2017JC012923
	Campagna C, Condit R, Ferrari M, Campagna j, Eder E, Uhart M, Vanstreels RET, Falabella V, Lewis MN (2025). Predicting Population Consequences of an Epidemic of High Pathogenicity Avian Influenza on Southern Elephant Seals. Marine Mammal Science, 2025; 0:e70	doi.org/10.1111/mms.70009
	Campagna C, Uhart M, Falabella V, et al. 2023. Catastrophic Mortality of Southern Elephant Seals Caused by H5N1 Avian Influenza. Marine Mammal Science 40: 1–4. https:// doi. org/ 10. 1111/ mms. 13101 .	doi.org/ 10. 1111/ mms. 13101
	Roquet F., Charrassin J.B., Marchand S., Boehme L., Fedak M., Reverdin G., Guinet C. (2011) Validation of hydrographic data obtained from animal-borne satellite-relay data loggers. Journal of Atmospheric and Ocean Technology. 28, 6. 787-801	doi.org/10.1175/2010JTECHO801.1
	Roquet F., Williams G., Hindell M.A., Harcourt R., McMahon C., Guinet C., Charrassin J.B., Reverdin G., Boehme L., Lovell P., Fedak M. (2014) A Southern Indian Ocean database of hydrographic	doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2014.28

	profiles obtained with instrumented elephant seals. (Nature) Scientific Data. doi:10.1038/sdata.2014.28	
	Bittig H. C., Steinhoff T, Claustre H., Fiedler B , Williams N. L., Sauzède R., Körtzinger A., Gattuso J. P. (2018) An Alternative to Static Climatologies: Robust Estimation of Open Ocean CO2 Variables and Nutrient Concentrations From T, S, and O2 Data Using Bayesian Neural Networks. Front. Mar. Sci. 5:328. doi: 10.3389/fmars.2018.00328	doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2018.00328
	Emerson S. R., & Hedges, J. I. (2008). "Chemical Oceanography and the Marine Carbon Cycle." Cambridge University Press.DOI: 10.1017/CBO9780511793202	doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511793202.007

APPENDIX 2: MAANTA NAUTILOS | SYSTEM CONCEPT EVOLUTION

Although other deployment methods were initially discussed for NAUTILOS activities, the target species considered in the scope of the project led to a towed non-invasive solution.

Once the towed solution was defined, the primary objective was to determine the optimal shape and volume to accommodate the oxygen sensor considered for the NAUTILOS solution (Deliverable 5.8). This analysis was conducted using Computer-Aided Design (CAD) methods for design conceptualization, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) techniques for forces and moments prediction, Finite Element Methods (FEM) for structural analysis, and in-house developed tools for stability and attitude assessment. Based on the CEiiA technical team evaluation, and further discussions with the IMAR team, it was determined that a single container to accommodate both electronics and the oxygen sensor could not be the optimal solution since it could significantly compromise the overall size and volume of the platform.

Although resin encapsulation was initially considered, the manufacturing and risk assessments ultimately led to the development of watertight metallic containers for the MAANTA NAUTILOS concept. The containers and lids (end caps) were thoroughly redesigned and structurally optimized to fulfill both operational requirements to withstand the harsh environment and extreme pressures (defined for the platform operational requirements; depth rate - 2000 m) while keeping the design as small as possible. This way, several materials were considered and studied for manufacturing. Although titanium would be a good fit, its raw material and manufacturing costs turned it an unsuitable option. Other options, such as stainless steel, were also considered but due to its higher density, i.e. weight, were also discarded. The final materials considered were Al 6061-T6 and Al 7075-T6. While the latter yields greater structural integrity, the former usually presents better resistance to corrosion for this kind of application. The Al 7075-T6 ended up to be the material adopted for the containers' components due to its exceptional strength and hardness, as well as availability on the market. All containers' components manufactured were then anodized to improve their corrosion resistance.

MAANTA NAUTILOS containers development focused also on the premise of being user-friendly and easy to operate, i.e. easy assembly/disassembly before, during, or after deployments. The final concept consists of two identical containers that differ solely in their end caps. Both payload components and containers were iteratively developed and redesigned to ensure all non-waterproof components would fit within the specified container diameter and length. The external shape of the MAANTA NAUTILOS platform, i.e. the buoyant halves, were only detailed once all payload shapes and dimensions were closed.

The integration of sensors on the containers was also crucial for this development, especially the sensors that need to be in contact with the environment for data reading and acquisition. This way, both temperature/pressure sensor and oxygen sensor integration were, following both suppliers' installation guidelines, fully customized to our solution. Figure A2 - 1 demonstrates the guidelines followed for the PyroScience oxygen sensor integration.

Figure A2 - 1: PICO-O2-SUB - Mounting of fiber connector in the lid (extracted from PYRO manual).

Once the containers' detailed design was closed, all other mechanical components were evaluated and customized to comply with the operational and environmental requirements defined in the scope of this project. A few payload configurations have been evaluated in terms of hydrodynamics and stability. Although all of them complied with the requirements, one of them outperformed in terms of hydrodynamics, and consequently, would cause less impact on the natural behaviour of the target species.

The final MAANTA NAUTILOS platform design integrates several components:

- Vertical and horizontal stabilizers, dimensioned using CFD methods to predict the surface area needed for these components to counteract and correct any undesired attitude during deployment, caused either by the forces and moments exerted by the fluid on other platform components or any other undesired external disturbances;
- Paddle wheel, a crucial component to measure the target species swimming speed, was also developed to handle pressures up to 200 bar, i.e. 2000 m depth, and correctly positioned to perform the readings needed to measure the velocity;
- Bracket, also very important since it allows the coupling between the platform and the target species, once the body harness-loop is attached to one of the front holes of the bracket and deployed on the animal. Besides this, it also allows for significant pitch corrections, before or after deployments, by moving the trim weights positioned on the bracket. This trim weights' position should always be assessed beforehand any deployment on a different target species since it should be adjusted according to the nominal swimming speed of the animal;
- Syntactic foams, i.e. buoyant halves, were developed to accommodate all these items while ensuring the optimal hydrodynamics and stability during deployments. It is important to note that the integration of any other component or the reallocation of the current items may affect the stability and attitude during deployments or even jeopardize the platform's recovery. Figure A2 - 2 illustrates the streamlines' behavior while the platform is being towed by the target species at a swimming speed of 4 m/s. On the other hand, Figure A2 - 3 illustrates the hydrodynamic studies performed for different target species.

Figure A2 - 2: Streamlines' behavior while the platform is being towed by the target species at a swimming speed of 4 m/s.

Figure A2 - 3: Hydrodynamic studies performed for different target species.

With respect to the stability assessment of the platform, it could be divided into two important analyses: the static and dynamic analysis. While the latter focus on the behavior of the tag during operation, the former aims to assure the tag will be retrieved after deployment. i.e, the platform shall in any event be able to return to its equilibrium position (antennas facing upwards) while floating at the surface otherwise it won't communicate through the antennas (satellite or VHF radio) and won't be recovered. Furthermore, one must also give special attention to where the waterline is while the platform is at the surface, since satellite antennas won't also communicate if their sensors are fully submerged.

One of the major challenges encountered during the project related to how to connect both containers using a communication cable that could remain stable at a depth of 2000 m. The considered communication cable selected had a suitable static minimum bend radius for the intended application, and a theoretical validation, at that time, up to 2000 meters (although it has been tested up to 1000 m).

To address this uncertainty, it was decided to proceed with this solution but perform hyperbaric tests to assess and ensure its performance.

An additional challenge, and the most significant through NAUTILOS WP7 activities, arose regarding the proper isolation of the lids with the cable. In detail, two different approaches were considered:

- The lids with cables encapsulated using epoxy resin. These methods involved exploring different materials, shapes, and design variations always following the guidelines provided either by the mechanical design team and the epoxy resin supplier;
- Cable penetrators for connecting the lids to the cable.

As it will be further described in detail, and it is summarized on Table A2 -1 that shows a summary of all MAANTA NAUTILOS events, including hyperbaric chamber testing, water leaks and successful missions, isolation of the lids with the cable proved, indeed, to be the most challenging aspect of MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag development. In consequence, since the preliminary MAANTA NAUTILOS concept in early 2023, the approach to effectively isolate the electronics, particularly the lids with the communication cable, has undergone three major conceptual design cycles: 2 of them with epoxy resins and rated for 2000m and a final one to with epoxy resins and rated for 1000 m (Table A2 - 1).

Table A2 - 1: MAANTA NAUTILOS three major conceptual design cycles, and complementary activities throughout NAUTILOS project.

ACTION	MAXIMUM DEPHT /PRESSURE	DATE	NOTES
MANTAA NAUTILOS design #1 (1 type of epoxy resin; 2000 m)			
Hyperbaric validation tests #1a - with success	50 bar	22/02/2023	OceanScan hyperbaric chamber - Matosinhos
Hyperbaric validation tests #1b - with success	200 bar	01/03/2023	IST hyperbaric chamber - Lisbon
WP6 HCMR cal/val activities	n.a.		Described in the Chapter V of deliverable 6.1
MANTAA NAUTILOS design #1 Shipping to Azores (one unit) - 07/05/2023			
IMAR test drops at sea - water leak #1	After a few minutes on water; maximum depth registered 80 m	05/07/2023	Water leaked in the first MAANTA NAUTILOS drop in Azores
Hyperbaric inspection - not possible to replicate the real case incident	50 bar	19/7/2023	Test up to 50 bar, at OceanScan hyperbaric chamber - Matosinhos, without water leak
MANTAA NAUTILOS design #2 (two types of epoxy resin; 2000 m)			

Hyperbaric validation tests #2 - with success	200 bar	28/02/2024	IST hyperbaric chamber - Lisbon
MANTAA NAUTILOS design #2 Shipping to Azores (first unit) - 19/03/2024			
IMAR test drops at sea - with success	43 bar	March and April 2024	2 successful drop tests in Azores
First tagged animal with success	47 bar	29/04/2024	1 attempt/ 1 successful deployment in Azores
MANTAA NAUTILOS design #2 Shipping to Azores (second unit, after success) - 21/05/2024			
IMAR offshore deployments - water leak #2 & #3 (on both units)	After approximately several hours of deployment and after enduring multiple deep dives to at least 200 m and 120 m of water depth	from 26/06/2024 to 28/06/2024	After a first and only successful deployment on 29/04/2024.
MANTAA NAUTILOS design #3 (without epoxy resins; 1000 m)			
Hyperbaric validation tests #3 with success	100 bar	31/07/2024	University of Aveiro hyperbaric chamber - Aveiro
MANTAA NAUTILOS design #3 Shipping to Azores (two) - 02/08/2024			
IMAR offshore deployments - No water leak with MANTAA NAUTILOS design #3	Maximum depth tested 1244.1 m	from 12/08/2024 to 29/05/2025 (Atlantic Ocean)	16 attempt/ 16 successful deployment (two units)

As described on Table A2 - 1 the water leaks affected the course of T7.5 activities. As shown in Table A2 - 1, two water leakage incidents were reported by IMAR in April 2023 and June 2024, leading to three major conceptual design cycles.

Before navigating through T7.5 activities, all concepts manufactured by CEiiA undergo testing to ensure it can handle the harsh environments and extreme pressures for which it was developed. These tests can either be performed in a real environment or dedicated laboratory. Since real environment testing typically involves higher costs together with some uncertainties, the laboratory testing is often preferred during an engineering development. This way, the main purpose of this testing is to subject the complete assembly (including metallic containers, buoyant halves, cables, epoxy resin, and other components directly exposed to water) to a short-duration hyperbaric test to assess the structural integrity of the components (electronics not included), i.e. no water leakage occurs. Figure A2 - 4 demonstrates one of the 3 hyperbaric chambers used to perform these tests, as well as the team that carried out the tests and Figure A2 - 5 show test results.

Figure A2 - 4: IST hyperbaric chamber facilities used for tests up to 200 bar, with MANTAA NAUTILOS design #1.

Figure A2 - 5: Graphic representation of a successful hyperbaric test as it happened on 01/03/2023.

Since the first incident occurred after a drop test registering the maximum of 80 m, the CEiiA team has decided to conduct a second set of laboratory tests using a different hyperbaric chamber located in Porto (Figure A2 - 6). This hyperbaric chamber is able to perform pressure tests on this kind of components up to 50 bar.

Figure A2 - 6: Oceanscan hyperbaric test chamber used to replicate the water leak.

These tests were considered inconclusive, since the containers performed well in this second laboratory as well. At that time, both CEiiA and IMAR teams debriefed about the possible causes, suspecting that the incident observed in the Azores could be caused by human error or instrumentation. After conducting a thorough inspection and engineering analysis, the CEiiA team decided to continue using the epoxy resin concept although now using a more flexible epoxy resin and implementing additional mechanical modifications in order to improve the design. The improvements included features such as improving the resin adhesion to the aluminum by removing the anodizing from the hole before applying the resin, using an epoxy cone to improve solution's strength near the lid, test hard anodizing, or even by applying epoxy inside the cable. The new units were successfully tested at 200 bar.

Furthermore, to minimize human error, a specialized tool was developed to facilitate the assembly/disassembly of the containers.

Unfortunately, even after all this effort, a second and third water leakage for both MAANTA NAUTILOS units after several hours of deployment and after enduring multiple deep dives to at least 200 m and 120 m of water depth. The data revealed that the tags stopped recording (possibly coincident with water leak) close to the surface, shallower than 50 m deep.

A microscopic analysis revealed the presence of salt crystals between the container and the resin, though no significant failure was observed within the resin system itself (Figure A2 - 7). It was concluded that the use of epoxy resin could no longer be justified in the scope of this project, despite the initial positive results from the hyperbaric chamber tests. During these tests, the equipment is only subjected to pressure for a couple minutes or hours, with fresh water and under controlled temperature conditions, which do not accurately reflect real-world deployment environments. A lesson was learned for further references, when testing epoxy encapsulated systems, one shall perform longer exposition tests, i.e. days or weeks continuously exposed to those environments.

Figure A2 - 7: Salt water microscopic evidence after the water leak.

Bearing this in mind, the chosen solution was to go back to one of the initial ideas of using cable penetrators. Given the NAUTILOS project timeline, it was decided to proceed with the 1000 m rated penetrator solution (unfortunately, only penetrators rated for up to 1000 m depth were in stock at that time). This retrofit involved a major effort across different CEiiA teams (logistics, management, mechanical, and electronics) to be able to deliver the solution back to the Azores late July 2024.

This third retrofit can be summarized in the following actions:

- Epoxy resin removal from the cable lids of both containers (electronics and oxygen sensor);
- Epoxy resin removal from the pressure sensor lid;
- WetLink penetrator integration, ensuring a secure seal following assembly instructions provided by the supplier;
- Lids retrofit to also include a zip tie hole (redundant safety system);
- Buoyant halves CNC retrofit to accommodate the new cable lids.

To further reduce the risk of water leakage through the cable lids, new lids were designed featuring a hole to lock with a zip tie. Additionally, a minor adjustment had to be made to the foams to ensure the new lids would fit in properly. This was mostly a redundant safety system to improve the sealing reliability.

Following the manufacturing phase, and right after the retrofit approval of the IMAR team, the CEiiA team proceeded with a preliminary hyperbaric chamber test in a third facility located at the University of Aveiro (Figure A2 - 8). This time, two tests were conducted, differing in the duration of exposure to maximum depth. The second test aimed to evaluate the system's behavior when subjected to longer expositions. This test lasted one hour at maximum pressure (100 bar), and both sets performed well too. Thus, one could conclude the validation of the penetrator-based concept has been successful.

Figure A2 - 8: Hyperbaric chamber test at UA with the third redesign on 29/07/2024 at 100 bar, with MANTAA NAUTILOS design #3.

Until the end of the project, the system did not exhibit any water leaks, even when submerged to depths deeper than 1000 m.

APPENDIX 3: MAANTA NAUILOS | AUTONOMY TESTS

The MAANTA NAUILOS platform was designed for deployments of up to one week, aligning with the expected duration of NAUILOS missions described in the Grant Agreement.

Autonomy was studied with different mission configurations to give the user the possibility to adapt their mission plan. A test rig (a form of hardware prototype built for lab testing to demonstrate the key functionality) was assembled with a moving paddle wheel (to simulate a swimming animal (Figure A3 - 1).

Figure A3 - 1: Test rig to estimate real autonomy.

The missions were configured to have all sensors enabled (IMU, pressure/temperature, light, velocity and oxygen) with a constant velocity “environment” (1,6 m/s). The results are described in Table A3 - 1. It is important to note that autonomy is higher with lower acquisition frequencies.

Table A3 - 1: Autonomy tests results.

	SAMPLE RATE (except Oxygen sensor) - Hz			
	1	10	20	50
OXYGEN RATE	a sample each 10 seconds			
PADDLE WHEEL VELOCITY (m/s)	1.6			
AUTONOMY	51h 10m	49h 47m	49h 30m	47h 14m

Although the maximum continuous autonomy is 2 days and a few hours (with the exception of 50Hz acquisition), the device can be configured to collect data for several days (up to 7, for example). In this sense, two strategies were suggested to IMAR:

- For deployments up to 48 hours, consider continuous data acquisition
- For deployments up to one week, consider non continuous mode, by configuring multiple periods over several days (i.e., duty cycles) until the total hours of data acquired reaches the estimated duration

Deployment time is a decision made by the IMAR team, considering the species to be tagged and ocean/weather conditions. Based on the IMAR configuration a specific GTR (Galvanic Timed Release) is considered to be used (GTR are available ranging from 1 to 100 days) thus conditioning the release time and deployment duration.

Throughout all NAUTILOS project, in order to assess the quality of the dissolved oxygen (DO) data, nine tests were performed in a controlled environment (i.e., laboratory) to compare the LITE readings with a third-party oxygen sensor (PreSens multiparameter) by IMAR team. Nine field tests were also conducted by casting the MAANTA NAUTILOS tag attached to a CTD instrument (AML-6 LGR, AML Oceanographic) to compare and assess the LITE tags performance. Some relevant results are presented below.

Dissolved oxygen sensor field test comparison – 2024/04/18

When the MAANTA NAUTILOS tag was shipped to IMAR, after the leaking issue in 2023, the IMAR team conducted a drop test with the MAANTA NAUTILOS attached to a CTD (Figure A4 -1) to compare/validate the dissolved oxygen readings in the sea before start deploying in sharks and rays in the Atlantic Ocean.

Figure A4 -1: MAANTA NAUTILOS tag attached to the CTD for a drop test in the Azores, Portugal.

The first Lite tag made available in 2024, the LITE6b36470, was compared with CTD cast to 400m depth. It's interesting to note that the oxygen concentration values at the surface are similar, both sensors capture the dissolved oxygen increase at about 100m and minimum at approximately 400m, with the LITE slightly overestimating depth (Figure A4 -2). More importantly, we observed a significant drift between the two sensors during the descent stage to the deepest section of the cast. After a short period at the deepest both sensors converged. The comparative analysis confirmed the operational reliability of the MAANTA NAUTILOS units, thereby validating the observed in-situ measurements and supporting the continuation of data processing and interpretation. This LITE unit was then used in a sixgill shark and in a shortfin mako shark in the Azores.

Figure A4 -2: Simultaneous 400 m cast of CTD and the LITE6b36470 sensor from April 2024.

APPENDIX 5: MAANTA NAUILOS | FIELD TESTS OCTOBER 2024

In this experiment, two LITE sensors (LITE6142647b and LITE6143647e) were simultaneously compared with the PreSens® multi-parameter, all measuring the same distilled 0% salinity water, at atmospheric pressure (1026 hPa). The tests started at 100% saturation and decreased to approximately 0%, by replacing O₂ with bubbling nitrogen. This controlled experiment showed that LITE and the PreSens multi-parameter O₂ measurements, from 100% saturation to approximately 0% followed a similar trend with some overlap. Yet, the LITE LITE6142647b shows consistent underestimations of O₂ saturation, compared with both LITE6143647e and the PreSens multi-parameter (Figure A5 - 1 and Figure A5 - 2; Table A5 - 1 and Table A5 - 2). The difference between both LITE sensors and between the PreSens multi-parameter and LITE6142647b are statistically significant (T-test: $t=-3.40$, $p=0.00037$; and $t=2.55$, $p=0.005$, respectively).

This difference is more pronounced at the higher range of the O₂ saturation, ie. the LITE6143647e starts off at values greater than 100% and then converges to the PreSens readings as soon as the O₂ saturation starts to decrease, and the difference remains relatively constant until approximately 20% O₂ saturation (Table A5 - 3). Below 20% O₂ saturation, both LITE sensors tend to underestimate saturation compared to PreSens multi-parameter.

Figure A5 - 1: Dissolved oxygen concentration (O₂ µmol/L; top) and saturation (O₂ % a.s.; bottom) profiles comparison for tags LITE6143647e (black) and LITE6142647b (yellow).

Despite deviations between LITE6143647e and the PreSens multi-parameter measurements (Figure A5 - 2), these differences are not statistically significant ($t=-0.73$; $p=0.23$), suggesting that the calibration protocol was effective and necessary. Moreover, the LITE6142647b (recently repaired by CEiiA after a incident that damaged the previous oxygen sensor cap) the dissolved oxygen readings differed statistically from the other LITE unit and the multiparameter, leading the IMAR team to conclude that the new sensor cap was not factory calibrated and, thus, required calibration before deployments.

Table A5 - 1: Dissolved oxygen concentration ($O_2 \mu\text{mol/L}$) and saturation ($O_2 \%$ a.s.) mean difference (delta), standard deviance (s.d.) and confidence interval (c.i.; 0.05) between the two LITE units (LITE6143647e and LITE6142647b).

	$O_2 \mu\text{mol/L}$	$O_2 \%$ a.s.
median	10.77	0.98
mean	34.93	11.93
s.d.	20.57	6.79
c.i.	2.96	0.98

Figure A5 - 2: Comparison of the dissolved oxygen saturation ($O_2 \%$ a.s.) profiles for tags LITE6143647e (black) and LITE6142647b (yellow) and PreSens multi-parameter (blue).

Table A5 - 2: Summary of the oxygen saturation ($O_2 \%$ a.s.) and concentration ($O_2 \mu\text{mol/L}$) of the two LITE units (LITE6143647e and LITE6142647b) and the PreSens multi-parameter; and the mean, standard deviation (s.d.) and confidence interval (c.i.; 0.05) for each sensor and of the difference (Δ) among the PreSens multi-parameter and two LITE units.

	LITE6143647e		LITE6142647b		Δ		PreSens	LITE6143647e	LITE6142647b
	% a.s.	$\mu\text{mol/L}$	% a.s.	$\mu\text{mol/L}$	Δ % a.s.	Δ $\mu\text{mol/L}$	% a.s.	Δ % a.s.	Δ % a.s.
median	18.39	50.61	10.93	29.17	7.49	21.60	15.49	-4.66	4.22
mean	37.74	104.05	25.80	69.12	11.94	34.98	34.91	-9.11	2.84
s.d.	37.57	104.06	29.54	79.57	8.12	24.61	38.11	9.09	4.30
c.i.	5.40	15.00	4.25	11.47	1.17	3.54	5.48	1.31	0.62

Table A5 - 3: Summary of the air-saturated dissolved oxygen (O2 % a.s.) mean difference (Δ) between each LITE unit (LITE6143647e and LITE6142647b) and the PreSens multi-parameter per Oxygen saturation intervals.

O2 % a.s.	mean Δ	
	LITE6142647b	LITE6143647e
100-80	-22.16	3.81
80-60	-22.91	-6.82
60-40	-15.99	-3.87
40-20	-8.74	0.41
20-10	-4.21	3.15
10-5	-2.53	4.15
5-2	-1.32	4.78
2-1	-0.59	5.30
<1	-0.21	5.55

Dissolved oxygen sensor field test comparison – 2024/12/02

Following the laboratory experiment, the IMAR team conducted field tests to verify the precision of the LITE tags' dissolved oxygen (DO) sensors by comparing in-situ measurements with CTD casts performed simultaneously at sea. Initial readings revealed a delay between the actual and recorded temperature values (Figure A5 - 3), followed by discrepancies in DO concentrations (Figure A5 - 4), which were ultimately attributed to insufficient water circulation over the pressure/temperature sensor diaphragm during dynamic vertical movements. A second source of error was identified in the calibration: the sensors, initially assumed to be factory-calibrated, required recalibration to ensure reliable data.

Figure A5 - 3: Simultaneous ~400 m cast (drop 1, left; drop 2, right) of CTD and the LITE6143647e showing the water temperature (°) from December 2024 in the Azores, Portugal.

Figure A5 - 4: Simultaneous ~400 m cast (drop 1, left; drop 2, right) of CTD and the LITE6143647e showing the dissolved oxygen concentration (umol/L) from December 2024 in the Azores, Portugal.

APPENDIX 6: SRDL-CTD-OXY | PRE-DEPLOYMENT TEST AND CALIBRATION

The tags and sensors were tested and pre-calibrated in an experimental set up conducted by SMRU (Scotland, UK).

The experiment consisted in plunging the tags in an 800L adiabatic temperature-controlled bath of sea-water, with a constant salinity of 34.857 PSU (± 0.0025), to stabilize temperature around six chosen values (± 0.1 mK), and each time, to record temperature and conductivity output of tag sensors (resp. ST and SC) at atmospheric pressure (1026 hPa). Reference salinity was measured with Autosal and Portosal salinometers, while reference temperature was measured with a SBE39 temperature sensor. Using the IPSS 78 algorithm, we deduced the reference electrical conductivity associated with the well-known bath salinity and temperature.

Temperature varied from -1.5 to 21.5°C. The resulting calibration range of conductivity was 17 to 38 mS/cm. The 0 mS/cm was added by measuring the conductivity response in dry air. The standard deviation (26) for reference temperatures and reference salinity are ± 0.0021 °C (EIT-90) and ± 0.0045 mS/cm respectively. Reference temperatures are related to ITS-90.

- Temperature sensors' behaviour was very good for every tags leading to uncertainties lower than 0.01°C for usable range of [-1.5, 21.5] °C (Table A6 - 1);
- Conductivity sensors' behaviour was good (~ 0.01 mS/cm) to excellent (< 0.01 mS/cm). Their static behaviour is 10 times better than the last generation of tags (Table A6 - 1);
- Oxygen tags were tested and simultaneously compared with Fast and Accurate Mobile Oxygen Measurement and Calibration Portable Dissolved Oxygen Meter (Mettler Toldo) in with a constant salinity close to 34 psu depending on the test conducted. The tests started at 100% saturation and decreased to approximately 0%, by replacing O₂ with bubbling nitrogen. Oxygen measurements provided by the tag were highly correlated to the measurements provided by the Mettler Toldo oxygen meter ($r^2 = 1$; with a slope coefficient of 1).

Table A6 - 1: The table below gives temperature and electrical conductivity for each calibration point, where a calibration point is a set of physical conditions where tag sensors output are recorded.

i	1	2	3	4	5	6
TEMPERATURE T_i (°C)	-1,5	1.4	4,4	7	10	21.5
SALINITY $S_i = s_0$ (psu)	35,2	35,2	35,2	35,2	35,2	10,2

